

Physically Modeling Kuiper Belt Contact Binaries

Thomas Leith

A thesis presented to the Department of Astronomy
in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Arts

April 8, 2016
Harvard College

Abstract

Previous photometric surveys of Kuiper Belt Objects (KBOs) have identified the first confirmed contact binary in that region (2001 QG₂₉₈), and given rise to estimates that between 10 and 20% of KBOs may be contact binaries—a significantly higher fraction than among Main Belt or NEAs. Thus far, definitive identification of trans-Neptunian contact binaries is only possible when their magnitude variability is greater than $\Delta\text{mag} \approx 1.0$. However, continuing observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈ have demonstrated that such a high magnitude variability only occurs during a brief window in each orbital period, when the target’s axis of rotation is perpendicular to the line of sight. In order to more comprehensively account for the effects of viewing geometry on contact binary lightcurves, we present a newly developed procedure for physically modeling and simulating observations of these objects. In doing so, we model contact binaries as Roche ellipsoids, treating them as rubble piles which uniformly fill gravitational equipotential surfaces. We then calculate the visible area of these model binaries over the course of a full rotation at a wide range of system geometries. Finally, we integrate over this area at each point in the binary’s rotation, accounting for the possibility of both rocky and icy surface types, and fitting the resultant synthetic lightcurve to observational data. Repeating this process for a large number of contact binary dimensions, mass ratios, and geometries provides a streamlined process for characterizing contact binaries from their lightcurves, even when they exhibit $\Delta\text{mag} < 1.0$. We intend to make this code publicly available for future studies of contact binaries throughout the Solar System.

Acknowledgements

This work would not have been possible without the advising, support, and assistance of Matthew Holman and Matthew Payne, without whom this study would never have been possible. We also wish to acknowledge the hard and skillful work of David Charbonneau in coordinating the undergraduate thesis program of the Harvard College Department of Astronomy. Having previously studied the Kuiper Belt contact binary 2001 QG₂₉₈, Pedro Lacerda very graciously provided us with both data and feedback on our methodology while it was in development. Numerous individuals were also enormously helpful in our efforts to obtain new data: Allyson Bieryla helped to coordinate observations on the Whipple Observatory 1.2-meter telescope (as well as reduction of those data), and Nick Moskovitz, Brian Skiff, and Dagmara Oszkiewicz did the same for observations at the Lowell Observatory Perkins 72” telescope. Assistance in reducing Perkins data was provided by Dan Avner and Phil Massey. The staff and resources of the Harvard College Library, the John G. Wolbach Library, and the NASA Astrophysics Data System were all vital in supplying the background literature

necessary to undertake this research. Patricia Gnazzo Pepper, Alana Ryan, and the entire staff of Currier House provided seemingly unending moral and logistical support throughout the creation of this work. Much of the data used in this study were taken using instruments located at the summit of Mauna Kea, which holds enormous cultural and spiritual significance to the native Hawaiian community. We are immensely grateful for the opportunity to make use of this important site for astronomical observations.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	The Trans-Neptunian Region	4
1.1.1	Discovery	8
1.1.2	Formation According to the Nice Model	11
1.1.3	Comparison with Main Belt and NEAs	13
1.2	Contact Binaries	17
1.2.1	Theoretical Contact Binary Formation Mechanisms	18
1.2.2	Contact Binary Lightcurve Characteristics	26
2	The Contact Binary 2001 QG₂₉₈	29
2.1	Identification as a Contact Binary	29
2.2	A Change in the Lightcurve of 2001 QG ₂₉₈	31
3	Observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈	37
3.1	Post-2010 Pan-STARRS Observations	37
3.2	Follow-Up Observations	38
3.3	Reduction of Raw Data	41
3.4	Photometry	41
3.5	Conversion from Apparent to Absolute Magnitude	42
3.6	Determination of Period and Phase Folding	43
3.7	Observational Results	45
4	The Challenge of Modeling Contact Binaries	46
4.1	Modeling Contact Binaries as Spheres	47
4.2	Modeling Contact Binaries as Ellipsoids	48
4.3	Modeling Binary Orbits	50
5	Simulating Lightcurves	51
5.1	An Analytical Approach to Simulated Lightcurves	52
5.2	Numerically Simulating Lightcurves	55

5.2.1	Determining the Limits of Integration	56
5.2.2	Reflectance	68
5.3	Library Generation	72
6	Analysis of Model Lightcurves	74
6.1	Creating a Lightcurve	74
6.2	Accounting for Phase Offset and χ^2 Fitting	75
6.3	Determination of Error	77
6.4	χ^2 Fitting Results	78
7	Conclusion	81
7.1	Future Directions	81
7.2	Summary	82

1 Introduction

1.1 The Trans-Neptunian Region

In recent years, the outermost reaches of the Solar System have become the focus of considerable attention in the astronomical community. Public interest was most notably drawn by the New Horizons mission, which in 2015 became the first spacecraft to visit the Kuiper Belt during its successful Pluto flyby. However, despite being undoubtedly the most famous member of its trans-Neptunian family, Pluto is by no means alone. In 1992 (62 years after Pluto’s discovery, and 14 years after the discovery of its companion Charon) the first additional Kuiper Belt Object (KBO) was identified: a 100-km-scale body known as 1992 QB₁ (Jewitt and Luu, 1992). Since then, its discovery has been joined by hundreds more, so that today we have a relatively clear picture of this distant and remarkable region of space.

The Kuiper Belt is a disk of rocky, icy bodies orbiting between 30 and 50 AU from the Sun—stretching from Neptune’s orbit to its 1:2 Mean Motion Resonance. Unlike the Asteroid Belt between Mars and Jupiter, the Kuiper Belt is a roughly torus-shaped region, populated by objects with a relatively wide range of orbital inclinations. These objects are overwhelmingly made up of ices: primarily water, methane, and ammonia; however, detailed spectroscopic observations are highly challenging due to the distance and faintness of KBOs (Emery, 2008). One thing that is well-established, however, is that – thanks to its complex evolution (discussed in section 1.1.2) and the gravitational influence of Neptune – it is a dynamically highly diverse region, consisting of several different classes of objects and surrounded by numerous relatives (a breakdown of orbital parameters of each KBO classification is shown in table 1.1):

1. *Resonant KBOs*: as their name suggests, these objects orbit in one of Neptune’s mean motion resonances (MMRs). The most notable example of a resonant KBO is Pluto, which orbits in the 2:3 MMR (other resonant KBOs lying in the 2:3 MMR are, as a result, known as “Plutinos”). However, many additional Neptunian MMRs are well-populated, including the 1:2 MMR and its constituent “twotinos.” One other dwarf planet, Haumea (7:12 MMR), is known to lie in a relatively weak orbital resonances with Neptune (Ragozzine and Brown, 2007).
2. *Classical KBOs*: the Classical Kuiper Belt is defined as the region between the 2:3 and 1:2 MMRs (in honor of the first KBO to be discovered, 1992 QB₁ these objects are sometimes referred to as “Cubewanos”). As their orbits are free from resonant gravitational interactions with Neptune, Classical KBOs typically have relatively circular orbits and low inclinations, distinguishing

Classification	a (AU)	e	i°
“Plutino” Resonant KBO	39-40	0.0 – 0.4	10-25
“Cold” Classical KBO	40-50	< 0.1	< 5
“Hot” Classical KBO	40-50	> 0.1	> 5

Table 1: Orbital characteristics of three classifications of KBOs. While numerous families of resonant KBOs exist in each of Neptunes MMRs, the “Plutino” population is shown here as its objects are the most abundant and well-characterized. Orbital parameters for KBOs in other Neptunian MMRs are similar to the Plutinos’, save for a (Yu et al, 1999; Elliott et al, 2005).

them from other Trans-Neptunian Objects (Elliot et al, 2005). They are typically sorted into one of two categories:

- (a) “Cold” Classical KBOs: “Cold” Classicals represent two thirds of all Classical KBOs, and have orbits that are inclined less than $i = 5^\circ$ and have eccentricities less than $e = 0.1$. Its members are distinguished from “Hot” Objects by their red color and propensity to form similar-size binaries, making them of particular interest for this study. This tendency is reflected in figure 1 (Elliot et al, 2005).
- (b) “Hot” Classical KBOs: The “Hot” Classicals show enormous heterogeneity in both their orbits and color. Some theories for the evolutionary pathways which produced the distinct “Cold” and “Hot” groups are discussed in section 1.1.2 (Elliot et al, 2005).

The dwarf planet Makemake and dwarf planet candidates Quaoar and Varuna are all Classical KBOs (Ore et al, 2009; Margot et al, 2002).

Binaries are particularly prevalent among the Plutino and “Cold” Classical KBO populations (the tendency of binary Classical KBOs to have low inclination is shown in figure 1). These objects are particularly interesting because the complex dynamics of binary formation provide a window into the formation of the Kuiper Belt (section 1.2.1). Fitting to physical models of binaries can also yield detailed physical information about them, further enhancing our understanding of the region in which they reside, as discussed throughout this work.

Several other categories of objects populate the region close to and beyond Neptune’s orbit, but are do not reside in the Kuiper Belt. We provide a brief outline of them here:

1. *Scattered Disk Objects*: The Scattered Disk is a region overlapping with the Kuiper Belt, ranging from the orbit of Neptune past 100 AU. In contrast to

Figure 1: Orbital semimajor axes and inclinations of Classical KBOs, drawn from Noll et al (2008). Binaries shown by filled circles, and non-binaries shown by unfilled circles. The clustering of binaries at low inclinations and semimajor axes between 42-45 AU is obvious, showing that a large percentage of these objects can be found among the “Cold” Classical population in the center of the Classical Kuiper Belt.

KBOs, whose orbits are stable (either in Neptunian MMRs or in the Classical Kuiper Belt), Scattered Disk Objects are vulnerable to being scattered elsewhere by Neptune’s gravity, and as such are found in an enormously wide range of orbital semimajor axes, eccentricities, and inclinations. The Scattered Disk is thought to be the source of the Solar-System’s short-period comets (Horner et al, 2003). Eris, the most massive Trans-Neptunian Object known, is a Scattered Disk Object.

2. *Centaurs*: orbiting in the outer Solar System between Jupiter and Neptune, these objects do not lie within the Kuiper Belt itself. However, it is likely that they originated as Scattered Disk Objects, which—through gravitational interactions with Neptune—were thrown onto planet-crossing orbits in much the same way that Jupiter can send Main Belt asteroids hurtling into the inner Solar System. Centaurs, then, are likely an intermediate step for Scattered Disk Objects which will ultimately be ejected from the Solar System

or thrown onto cometary orbits, and thus are dynamically and evolutionarily linked to other Trans-Neptunian Objects.

3. *Detached Objects and Sednoids*: These dynamical families are essentially unlinked to their closer-in counterparts. Detached Objects are those whose perihelia are so distant that they are unaffected by Neptune's gravity not by settling into an orbital resonance or the Classical Kuiper Belt, but simply because they are so enormously far away. Those bodies whose perihelia are greater than 75 AU are termed Sednoids, after the minor planet Sedna (whose extremely elliptical orbit passes from 76 AU at perihelion to 937 AU at aphelion). These objects are of great interest, in part because their orbits suggest that they may have been gravitationally influenced by an undiscovered Ninth Planet or captured from a star which formed near the Sun (Batygin and Brown, 2016; Morbidelli et al, 2004).
4. *The Oort Cloud*: The even more distant Oort Cloud is the theorized source of long-period comets, comprising a spherical shell of icy planetesimals ranging from 2,000 to as much as 150,000 AU (0.75 pc, or about half the distance to Proxima Centauri) from the Sun (Brasser and Morbidelli, 2013). At such great distances, the Sun's gravity is weak enough that both nearby stars and the galaxy itself are capable of disrupting objects' orbits (Weissman, 1983). The Oort Cloud was likely populated during the period of giant planet migration in the early Solar System, as discussed in section 1.1.2. However, due to the exotic nature of these regions and their sheer distance from the Kuiper Belt and Scattered Disk, we consider them to be beyond the scope of this study.

Figure 2: Dynamical map of known KBOs showing semimajor axis plotted against eccentricity (top, with curved lines showing $q = 30$ AU and $q = 40$ AU) and inclination (bottom), from Levinson et al (2008). Mean Motion Resonances with Neptune are shown by vertical black lines, with resonant KBOs represented by black dots, classical KBOs as red dots, and objects currently undergoing encounters with Neptune as green dots. Note the significant clustering along Neptunian MMRs and the density of low-inclination (“cold”) classical KBOs between the 3:5 and 1:2 MMRs.

1.1.1 Discovery

The discovery of Pluto in 1930 by Clyde Tombaugh was an enormous milestone in our understanding of the Solar System—no less significant than those of Uranus and Neptune had been, Pluto’s 2006 “demotion” notwithstanding. Clearly Tombaugh’s

colleagues believed as much: when Lowell Observatory announced Pluto’s discovery (on Percival Lowell’s 75th birthday, no less) their language bordered on Biblical, proclaiming that “In the little cluster of orbs which scampers across the sidereal abyss under the name of the Solar System there are, be it known, nine instead of a mere eight, worlds” (Davies et al, 2008). Yet the idea that there might be far more than a mere nine “orbs” in that cluster was not a new one. The theorization and discovery of the Kuiper Belt is covered at length in Davies et al (2008), and we relate a condensed version of that history here.

The presence of an asteroid belt between Mars and Jupiter had been known since the mid-1800s. Less than a year had passed since Pluto’s discovery before Frederick Leonard was speculating that “is there any reason to suppose that there are not other, probably similarly constituted, members revolving around the Sun outside of the orbit of Neptune? Indeed, it may ultimately be found that the Solar System consists of a number of zones, or families, of planets, one within the other... Is it not likely that in Pluto there has come to light the *first* of a *series* of ultra-Neptunian bodies, the remaining members of which still await discovery but which are destined eventually to be detected?” (Leonard, 1930)

This idea was carried forward by the Irish astronomer Kenneth Edgeworth (after whom the Kuiper Belt is sometimes more formally referred to as the “Edgeworth-Kuiper Belt”). In a manuscript which he would continue to update and revise from 1938 to 1949, Edgeworth asserted that the Solar System’s planets had condensed out of a disk of spinning gas and dust, which itself comprised the leftover material that formed the Sun—an idea dating back to Immanuel Kant’s *Universal Natural History and Theory of the Heavens* (1755) and Laplace’s *Exposition du Systeme du Monde* which we know refer to as the Nebular Hypothesis (Jeffereys, 1923; Edgeworth, 1949). He went on to state that, because the density of the protoplanetary disk would have steadily decreased at greater heliocentric distances, it was unlikely that giant planets could have formed past Neptune. Rather, he speculated that in “in the region outside the orbit of Neptune... condensations would be small and numerous... and the region is probably populated by a very large number” of planetesimals (Edgeworth, 1949). In many ways, Edgeworth was ahead of his time—while positing the presence of numerous additional planetesimals beyond Neptune, he also voiced doubts as to whether Pluto was truly a planet, or something more analogous to the large bodies of the Main Belt. A decade later, he was also among the first to speculate that such bodies would be rubble piles (or as he put it, “heaps of gravel”) rather than compacted planetary material—an important and necessary realization for much of the analysis and modeling performed in this study (Edgeworth, 1961).

Before any of Edgeworth’s claims could be truly substantiated, numerous astronomers would attempt to tackle the twin questions of what had happened to the

primordial debris disk beyond Neptune and what the origins of both the short- and long-period comets were. The presence of the Oort cloud had been hypothesized by Ernst Opik and Jan Oort, providing a satisfactory explanation for the origins of the long-period comets. However, Oort’s suggestion that short-period comets were Main Belt asteroids whose orbits had been elongated by Jupiter seemed implausible to the Dutch-American astronomer Gerard Kuiper. He suggested that comets were “snowballs,” condensed from a ring of primordial material beyond Neptune and thrown into the inner Solar System through interactions with Pluto (Kuiper, 1951).

Fred Whipple subsequently recognized that Pluto alone was far too small—even according to contemporary overestimates of its size—to have such an enormous influence on its neighborhood. Rather, he speculated that, instead of being the singlehanded work of Pluto, a ring of icy bodies massing up to $20 M_{\oplus}$ could be interrupting the orbits of smaller snowballs and hurling them toward the Sun. While his mass estimate was orders of magnitude too high, and he mistook the far-reaching influence of Neptune for that of Pluto-like bodies, Whipple’s fundamental idea of an icy transneptunian belt was a correct one. However, he also noted that even 100 km-scale bodies would be undetectable using the technology of the day (Whipple, 1964). A decade and a half later, Fernandez (1980) expanded on Whipple’s theory that a ring of icy bodies beyond Neptune was the source of the short-period comets, but was skeptical of the Whipple’s high estimate of its mass. Instead, he correctly suggested that Neptune, in conjunction with close encounters between small bodies, was sufficient to hurl the distant “snowballs” into the inner Solar System.

The next step in confirming the presence of the Kuiper Belt came when Duncan et al (1988) noted that the observed distribution of short-period comets’ inclinations was far too small for them to all have originated in a spherical (Oort) cloud. Short-period comets’ orbits all lie extremely close to the ecliptic. Naturally, then, they must have originated in or near this plane, adding to the evidence for a cometary reservoir orbiting the Sun beyond Neptune. Duncan et al (1988) first proposed that this reservoir be named the “Kuiper Belt.” Stern (1991) subsequently put together a definitive theory which tied together previous studies predicting the presence of both planetesimals and a cometary reservoir beyond Neptune. He went on to connect this theory to Neptune and Uranus’ high axial tilts and Triton’s retrograde orbit: since the latter were already thought to be the result of large collisions and the former indicated that it was a captured moon, both were indicative of many previously unknown objects lurking in the outer Solar System.

Stern (1991) went on to point out that modern large-scale sky surveys in the optical and infrared would now be able to detect 100-km to 1000-km-sized bodies

out to distances of 100 AU. The hunt for objects lying in the theorized Kuiper Belt thus became a major pursuit of Solar System scientists from the late 1980s into the early 1990s. For several years, major surveys—many of them still relying on photographic plates and blink cameras not much different from Clyde Tombaugh’s—scanned large chunks of the ecliptic without success. However, using two CCDs mounted on the University of Hawaii 2.2-meter telescope late in the summer of 1992, Jewitt and Luu successfully imaged an object designated 1992 QB₁ which showed promise of lying in an orbit entirely beyond Neptune’s. Months of followup (Marsden, 1992; Jewitt and Luu, 1993) confirmed that it was indeed the first true KBO discovered since Pluto.

The first drop became a trickle as more KBOs were discovered the following year (e.g. Luu and Jewitt, 1993), and—as tends to be the case—the trickle gradually grew to a flood (Trujillo, 2008). What had once been seen as a desolate region of space is now known to be richly (if thinly, when one takes into account its size) populated by a dynamically highly diverse array of minor planets. Having established its presence, the question remaining to astronomers then became: how exactly did the Kuiper Belt form?

1.1.2 Formation According to the Nice Model

Like most debris disks, the Kuiper Belt is an amalgamation of material left over from the primordial Solar System (Vitense et al, 2010). However, the exact process by which it formed is a complex one, best understood through the lens of the Nice model of planet formation. According to the Nice model (Morbidelli et al, 2005; Gomes et al, 2005; Tsiganis et al, 2005), the early Solar System was far more compact than it is today, with the four gas giant planets orbiting at heliocentric distances between 5.5 and 14 AU and with Uranus orbiting beyond Neptune. Had these planets—particularly the outlying ice giants—formed at their current orbits, the density of Hydrogen and Helium gas in their orbital neighborhoods would have been too low for them to accrete $10 M_{\oplus}$ atmospheres during the lifetime of the disk (Desch, 2007). The migration of the giant planets to their present locations occurred through an exchange of angular momentum with small, icy bodies formed in a dense debris disk populated with numerous planetesimals—an idea which predates the Nice model to at least 1984, when Fernandez and Ip (1984) happened upon it while seeking the origin of near-parabolic comets.

This debris disk would ultimately evolve into the Kuiper Belt. However, this proto-Kuiper belt was vastly different from what it would become. The most significant distinction was its size: at this stage in the Solar System’s evolution, the debris disk beyond the giant planets contained thousands of Pluto-sized objects, with a total mass of approximately $35 M_{\oplus}$, hundreds of times more than the mass of the Kuiper Belt today. Such a high mass is necessary to explain the formation

of the KBOs we can observe from Earth. Given the vast expanse of the Kuiper Belt and the low density of objects inhabiting it, the KBOs we now observe in could not have formed at today's density (Gladman et al, 2001).

The fate of this tremendous missing mass—virtually all of the material that once existed in the debris disk beyond the gas giants—lies in the complex movements of the giant planets as they made their way from the orbits in which they formed to their present positions. Within a few million years of forming, the innermost planetesimals populating the outer disk began to find their way onto planet-scattering orbits. As they migrated inward, they exchanged angular momentum with each giant planet until encountering Jupiter. This process continued until Jupiter and Saturn crossed their mutual 1:2 mean motion resonance.

The Jupiter-Saturn resonance-crossing event increased both planets' orbital eccentricities and greatly accelerated the destabilization of the early Solar System. In addition to destabilizing as many as 90% of the Main Belt asteroids, another notable effect was to enormously increase Uranus and Neptune's eccentricities—at times to values as high as $e \approx 0.4$ (Levison et al, 2008). This triggered a series of encounters between the two ice giants. It is during this time that Neptune crossed Uranus' orbit, and both planets plowed outward through the debris disk of the outer Solar System.

Over 99% of the disk's objects were destabilized and thrown into the inner Solar System as part of this process. They subsequently either were ejected or impacted the terrestrial planets in the cataclysmic Late Heavy Bombardment: a period during which the inner Solar System was pelted with a disproportionately large number of asteroids (Gomes et al, 2005). Simulations of gas giant migration show the resonance-crossing event closely coinciding with petrological dating of the Late Heavy Bombardment to approximately 4.1 to 3.8 Ga. This timing lends further support to the Nice model (Gomes et al, 2005). Most of those objects that did not impact the terrestrial planets had their eccentricities enormously increased by encounters with Jupiter and began to form the Oort cloud, while the remainder were either captured by giant planets as irregular satellites (Nesvorný et al, 2007) or became trapped in Trojan orbits (Morbidelli et al, 2005).

However, Neptune's high eccentricity also increased the width of its mean-motion resonances. This phenomenon reached its peak when Neptune was at a semimajor axis between 27 and 29 AU, at which point the resonances between Neptune's orbit and its MMRs overlapped each other (Levinson et al, 2008). The result was a chaotic region in which trans-Neptunian objects wandered freely until they were on orbits covering the entire region of the Kuiper Belt. Dynamical friction with these objects then diminished Neptune's eccentricity, and the orbits of trans-Neptunian objects then stabilized.

The varying fates of those objects that remained in the outer Solar System

can reproduce the enormous complexity and diversity of trans-Neptunian objects (Horner et al, 2003):

1. *Resonant KBOs* were primordially locked into orbital resonances with Neptune, which have remained in place since the stabilization of Neptune’s orbit.
2. *Classical KBOs* resided in stable orbits between Neptune’s MMRs following the stabilization of Neptune’s orbit.
3. *Scattered Disk Objects* remained in orbits which continued to be perturbed by Neptune’s following the stabilization of its orbit.
4. *Centaur*s are Scattered Disk Objects pulled onto unstable orbits interior to Neptune.
5. *Detached Objects and Sednoids* were too distant to have interacted with Neptune as its orbit stabilized.
6. *The Oort Cloud* consists of the rocky and icy bodies which were drawn into the inner Solar System during giant planet migration, then thrown onto high-*e*, high-*i* orbits by gravitational interactions with Jupiter.

The Nice model is not an entirely conclusive explanation for the genesis of the Kuiper Belt or the outer Solar System more generally. Some open questions remain, including the number of objects which formed in the early Kuiper Belt and survived its early instability, and exactly why Uranus and Neptune swapped places (that result is one which is dictated by surface density profiles of the early Solar System, but is not fully understood from a dynamical perspective). However, no other model succeeds in explaining the evolution of the outer Solar System as successfully, and it is likely that it will remain fundamentally the same as such details are resolved (Desch 2007; Morbidelli, 2010).

1.1.3 Comparison with Main Belt and NEAs

Given that much of our discussion of contact binaries in section 1.2 will rely on comparisons between objects in the Kuiper Belt and the more easily-studied Main Belt and NEA populations, it is worth outlining some of the similarities and differences between these two regions.

1.1.3.1 Dynamical Stability and Instability

Both the Kuiper Belt and Main Belt are inextricably dynamically linked to a nearby gas giant—Neptune in the case of the Kuiper Belt, and Jupiter in the case

of the Main Belt. The most notable effect of Jupiter’s gravity on the Main belt manifests at its Mean Motion Resonances. Due to Jupiter’s enormous gravity, asteroids in Jupiter-resonant orbits are rapidly destabilized, leading to the asteroids migrating outward or plunging into the terrestrial planet region where they will ultimately impact a planet (Bottke 2002). As a result, all objects which originally formed in or near resonances with Jupiter have been eliminated from the Main Belt. Other asteroids frequently pass through these resonances as a result of the Yarkovsky effect, wherein rotating objects receive slight prograde or retrograde thrust due to asymmetric thermal radiation caused by their rotation. When this orbital evolution places asteroids into a Jupiter MMR, they too are quickly destabilized (Burns et al, 1979). This process has yielded evident gaps in the Main Belt population at each Jupiter MMR, and essentially bookends the Main Belt between the 4:1 resonance at 2.06 AU and the 2:1 orbital resonance at 3.28 AU.

Resonances in the Kuiper Belt show a remarkable contrast with the Main Belt. Rather than destabilizing resonant bodies, Neptunian resonances provide some of the most stable islands within the Kuiper Belt, analogous to the large population of stable Jupiter trojans which lie in and around Jupiter’s L_4 and L_5 Lagrangian points (Morbidelli et al, 2005). As discussed in section 1.1 and shown in figure 2, a large population of resonant KBOs orbits within Neptune’s MMRs, including the Pluto system. As Neptune is six times farther from the Sun than Jupiter, its resonances are correspondingly farther apart. The Classical Kuiper Belt population is far more analogous to the Main Belt, lying in the region between two major resonances where Neptune’s influence is minimal. The Main Belt has no strict analog to the Scattered Disk, as objects in unstable orbits at high inclinations are rapidly eliminated from the inner Solar System through interactions or impacts with the rocky planets (Bottke et al, 2005).

1.1.3.2 Solar Flux

Perhaps the most significant environmental distinction between the Kuiper Belt and Main Belt is the influence of solar flux on objects in each respective region. The Yarkovsky effect is powerfully evident in the Main Belt, particularly when acting on small bodies, and is a main driver of Main Belt asteroids’ orbital evolution. However, given that it lies fifteen times farther from the Sun than the Main Belt, the solar flux in the Kuiper Belt is 225 times less than in the Main Belt at its innermost extent. Radiative processes like the Yarkovsky effect are thus correspondingly lessened when acting on trans-Neptunian objects. This is discussed in greater detail in section 1.2.1.

1.1.3.3 Composition

The constituent objects in the Main Belt and beyond Neptune bear little compositional resemblance to each other. Main Belt objects are overwhelmingly made up of organics and silicates that are essentially the leftover material which remained in that region of space without forming into protoplanets (DeMeo et al, 2009). Another small but significant minority of Main Belt asteroids are made up of the remnants or impact ejecta of differentiated protoplanets. These are iron-nickel asteroids which formed in planetary cores (Bottke et al, 2006), and basaltic asteroids which originated in differentiated mantles. Volatiles such as water and methane are rare in the Main Belt except when bound into rocks and clays, as their typical lifetimes would have been very short in the far warmer region closer to the Sun (DeMeo et al, 2009).

Beyond Neptune, this situation is almost exactly reversed. While organics and silicates are present, and likely make up the cores of larger planetesimals such as Pluto, KBOs are overwhelmingly made up of ices such as water and CO₂ rather than rock. The orbit of Neptune is well beyond the “snow line” of all common volatile molecules, and so planetesimal formation in this region was dominated by agglomerations of icy water, ammonia, and hydrocarbons (Jewitt and Luu, 2004). These substances likely constitute the majority of all trans-Neptunian objects.

While objects in the Kuiper Belt and Main Belt are compositionally very distinct, they are structurally quite similar. Both KBOs and Main Belt asteroids are mostly “rubble piles.” This means that they are not monoliths, but rather loosely bound agglomerations of material held together only by self-gravity (Sanchez and Scheers, 2014; Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004). This means that both families of objects are easily disrupted and distorted by collisions and tidal interactions, and is of great significance to the modeling effort laid out in Chapter 4.

1.1.3.4 Collision Rates

Directly comparing collision rates in the Main Belt and in the Kuiper Belt is difficult and necessarily somewhat imprecise. In addition to depending heavily on the density of objects within each region (which varies widely across the Main Belt, and even more so across the Kuiper Belt), the likelihood of an impact on a given object is also dependent on its surface area, gravitational field, orbital parameters (a , e , and i) and dynamic stability. Several studies (e.g. Levison et al, 2000) have focused on the rate at which TNOs scattered interior to Neptune will impact the giant planets, but there has been no detailed assessment of impact rates within the Kuiper Belt itself. Zahnle et al (2003) estimate that $d > 100$ km objects impact Pluto at a rate of $2.3_{-1.2}^{+2.3} \times 10^{-11}$ per annum. However, this is heavily influenced

by Pluto’s large (for the Kuiper Belt) gravitational field and the fact that it lies at the innermost edge of the Kuiper Belt. Thus, it cannot be taken as representative of KBOs more generally, particularly KBOs outside of the 3:2 Neptunian MMR. Without additional study, no meaningful quantitative comparison can yet be made between impact rates in the Kuiper Belt and Main Belt.

1.1.3.5 Frequency and Type of Binaries

The fractional abundance of binaries in the trans-Neptunian, Main Belt, and Near-Earth object populations are all questions of active and continuing interest. The definitive work to date for NEAs is that of Margot et al (2002), who reviewed three years of cataloged radar observations of over 50 NEAs with diameter $d > 200$ m. In it, they found a binary fraction of approximately 16% in the NEA population, which agreed closely with prior estimates of 15% and 17% from tidal-disruption studies and lightcurve surveys (Margot et al, 2002). The predicted binary fraction in the Main Belt is significantly lower: both Merline et al (2002) and Margot and Brown (2001) found it to be in the vicinity of 2% of all observed Main Belt asteroids, which they believed to be representative of that entire population.

Among all binary asteroid populations, an active area of research is the fractional abundance of contact binaries. A contact binary is exactly what its name implies: a pair of objects, typically of a mass ratio of order unity (though there are examples where this is not the case), which are in contact (additional background on contact binaries, including theorized formation pathways, is provided in section 1.2). The first “binary” asteroid to be discovered, Ida and its companion Dactyl, is better thought of as an asteroid with a moon, given that Dactyl is only 10% the diameter of Ida and orbits it at a wide separation (Merline et al, 2002). This arrangement is fairly typical of Main Belt binaries, though their Near-Earth counterparts are likelier to have a mass ratio closer to unity. A number of Main Belt asteroids have been identified as having moons, but thus far 216 Kleopatra is the only known contact binary in that region. One Jupiter Trojan, 624 Hektor, is also suspected to be a contact binary (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004). While more binaries are both known and suspected among NEAs than in the Main Belt (for reasons discussed in section 1.2.1), these, too, are likely to be overwhelmingly non-contact binaries.

Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) suggest that contact binaries are likely to make up a far higher fraction of KBOs than either Main Belt asteroids or NEAs. Based on one detected contact binary in a sample of 34 KBOs (2001 QG₂₉₈, discussed in Chapter 2), they calculate the probability of the Earth lying within 10° of the equator of a randomly oriented KBO binary, and found that the fractional abundance of other contact binaries was likely to be approximately 17%, though

Figure 3: The discovery image of asteroid 243 Ida’s companion Dactyl (Merline et al, 2002). The Ida/Dactyl binary is, quite evidently, not a contact binary, as Dactyl is a small fraction the size of its parent body. Such binaries are far more common in the Main Belt than contact binaries (Richardson and Walsh, 2006).

they offer no uncertainty in this measurement and it will likely require revision as more objects are observed. Using a separate method which treated the contact binary as a distorted ellipsoid, they predicted a fractional abundance of 10%. While their sample size was too low to yield definitive conclusions, their work suggests that the contact binary fraction in the Kuiper Belt likely does lie in the vicinity of 10-20%. This is a substantially higher fraction than among Main Belt asteroids (2%) or NEAs (16%). If this is the case, it lends credence to the theorized methods of contact binary formation discussed in section 1.2.1.

1.2 Contact Binaries

Contact binaries have been identified throughout the Solar System, from the terrestrial planet region (e.g. 25143 Itokawa) to the Main Belt (e.g. 216 Kleopatra) to the Kuiper Belt (e.g. 2001 QG₂₉₈ (Hirabayashi et al 2009, Descamps et al 2011, Sheppard and Jewitt 2004)). The first to be discovered were NEAs, many of whom have been identified as such using radar observations (Benner, 2015). Since then, two contact binaries have been visited by spacecraft: the Near-Earth Apollo asteroid 25143 Itokawa, visited by the Hayabusa spacecraft in 2005 (Hirabayashi et al, 2010) and the comet 67P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko, visited by Rosetta in 2014 (Sierks et al, 2015).

Due to the wealth of information provided by those two spacecraft, Itokawa and 67P are useful for illustrating the large-scale physical properties of contact binaries. Contact binaries tend to exhibit a double-lobed shape, with each component of

Figure 4: Two contact binaries: asteroid 25143 Itokawa (left) and comet 67P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko. Both display the double-lobed shape typical of contact binaries, with a neck or bridge of material connecting two otherwise separate sections (Credit: ISAS/JAXA and ESA).

the binary a recognizably separate section from the other (see 4). These two sections are usually connected by a narrower neck or bridge of material that has accumulated around the binary’s center of mass.

Like most asteroidal binaries, the component bodies of the pre-contact binary are tidally locked, and the orbit of the pair becomes the rotation of the single body once they merge. Contact binaries are also like more typical asteroids in that they are most often rubble piles rather than monoliths, as discussed in section 1.1.3.3 (Walsh and Richardson, 2005). Their material is loosely bound by self-gravity, leaving them prone to tidal distortion and elongation as a result. The component parts of most contact binaries tend to be tidally elongated ellipsoids rather than spheres. Contact binaries form from wider binaries through the several different processes discussed in section 1.2.1.

1.2.1 Theoretical Contact Binary Formation Mechanisms

All theories of contact binary formation adhere roughly to the same general formula. To begin with, a single object is disrupted entirely, leading to debris which coalesces into two rubble piles which are gravitationally bound into orbit around one another at a distance. This non-contact binary is then forced into a closer orbit, and perhaps a collision, due to a loss of angular momentum or other disruption of their orbital system.

However, what processes lead to this “tightening” of the binary’s orbit is an active area of debate, and one for which numerous theories have been proposed. Due to the diversity of environments throughout the Solar System, contact binary formation may well occur due to different processes in various regions.

1.2.1.1 Rotational Fission due to YORP and BYORP

An important mechanism which has a strong influence on asteroids and other small bodies from the inner Solar System out to the Main Belt is the Yarkovsky-O’Keefe-Radzievskii-Paddack (hereafter, YORP) effect. The YORP effect is a summation of four related asymmetries in the balance of radiative forces. The Yarkovsky effect, identified by Ivan Yarkovsky in 1900, describes how a rotating asteroid will absorb radiative energy on its sunward-facing side, and due to thermal inertia later radiate it away later and in a different direction due to its rotation. This asymmetry produces a small net force along the direction of motion of the asteroid along its orbit. The resulting acceleration will change the semimajor axis of its orbit. The direction of rotation changes the sign of the Yarkovsky effect. Prograde-rotating bodies spiral away from the sun, and retrograde-rotating bodies spiral toward it (Opik 1951). This change in orbital semimajor axis da/dt occurs at a rate proportional to a^{-2} (Bottke et al, 2006).

Half a century after Yarkovsky, Radzievskii recognized that albedo variation across the surface of an object could, in conjunction with the Yarkovsky effect, steadily increase asteroids’ rotation rates: in the case of an asteroid with a high-albedo side and low-albedo side, the increased amount of sunlight reflected off the high-albedo side would cause a torque. As most asteroids are loosely amalgamated rubble piles, Radzeivskii recognized that “spin-up” due to this effect could ultimately disrupt small bodies entirely (Radzievskii 1954). However, this seemed an unlikely scenario at the time, as most Solar System bodies have relatively uniform albedos (as discussed in section 2.1). But in 1975, Paddack and Rhee showed that the asymmetric shape of objects had an even stronger torquing effect on small bodies. This, too, could lead to increased rotation speeds which could cause complete rotational disruption (Paddack and Rhee, 1975). This is the YORP effect.

The strongest evidence for rotational disruption by the YORP effect was observed in 2013, when the active main-belt asteroid (or “main-belt comet”) P/2013 R3 was observed disintegrating due to rotational spin-up caused by the YORP effect as shown in figure 5. (Jewitt et al 2014). A disintegration event will usually yield a dynamically related family of asteroids. However, rubble piles can also split into a pair of smaller gravitationally bound piles due to rotational fission, yielding a binary system (Paddack and Rubincam, 2007).

For this newly created binary to come into contact, we must next consider the influence of the “binary YORP” (or BYORP) effect. Since binary asteroids are likely to be tidally locked, they can be thought of as an extreme case of a highly asymmetric body (Cuk and Burns, 2005). This makes their orbits around one another particularly susceptible to the disruptive effects of YORP. The resulting torque can dramatically modify the pairs’ orbit, causing them either to spiral

Figure 5: Hubble Space Telescope observations of the disintegrating Main Belt asteroid P2013 R/3, drawn from Jewitt et al (2014). Images on the left are raw data and those on the right have been filtered to suppress the coma. The projected antisolar direction is shown by a yellow arrow, and the negative velocity vector by a green arrow. After breaking apart due to the YORP effect, P2013 R/3 has been segregated into three distinct regions of debris (labeled A, B, and C). While the pieces are moving apart from another too fast to re-form, similar cases with lower relative velocities could ultimately aggregate into a contact or near-contact binary.

outward from, or inward toward, their shared center of mass. The latter case will lead to a low-velocity collision in which the two bodies fuse together into a contact binary (Jacobson and Scheeres, 2014).

YORP and BYORP are significant effects in the Main Belt and NEA populations (Jacobson et al, 2014). Their effect is lessened in the case of KBOs in the more distant reaches of the Solar System. The solar flux is hundreds of times weaker beyond the orbit of Neptune compared to the inner Solar System and Main Belt (Marcus et al, 2011), as discussed in section 1.1.3.2. The Yarkovsky effect is still capable of inducing slow orbital drift depending on a given object’s orbital semimajor axis, little attention has been given to the strength of other radiative effects at such great distances from the Sun. However, given the small solar flux in the Kuiper Belt, we consider YORP and BYORP to be unlikely mechanisms of contact binary formation in that region.

1.2.1.2 Catastrophic and Near-Catastrophic Impacts

Numerous satellites throughout the Solar System are known to be the products of significant impacts. The most notable example is the Moon, which formed via a Mars-sized impactor colliding with the Earth. The resulting debris then accumulated into a satellite. This is called the Giant Impact Hypothesis (Canup and Asphaug, 2001). A similar process has been invoked to explain the formation of asteroidal satellites. The case of the asteroid 243 Ida and its satellite Dactyl is an example (Durda, 1995).

Broadly speaking, there are three means by which an impact could subsequently lead to the creation of a binary (Weidenschilling, 1989):

1. *Impact Ejecta* from a direct but non-catastrophic impact entering orbit around its parent body. Since asteroids are typically nonspherical in shape, it is possible that an asteroid could rotate 180° before ejecta could re-impact, potentially allowing the ejecta to “miss” the surface.
2. *Grazing Impact* between two bodies, dramatically altering and increasing the rotation rate. Since most asteroids are loosely bound rubble piles, this rapid spin-up could subsequently lead to rotational fission of the body, in the same way that spin-up and fission can occur due to the YORP effect. Once the asteroid has broken up, the resulting debris can then coalesce into a binary.
3. *Catastrophic impact* causing the total fragmentation of an asteroid. Such cases would yield enormous amounts of dynamically linked debris. It is likely that some pairs, or in rare cases triplets or quadruplets, of asteroidal fragments would be ejected at similar velocities and thus stay gravitationally bound to one another.

While the first mechanism is likely to be the most common one, it is also the least likely to yield a long-term stable binary. Any ejecta which were to “slip” into orbit through such a mechanism must either have its orbit rapidly altered by other gravitational effects, or else re-impact the surface within a few orbital periods. Even in scenarios where a stable orbit is reached, impact ejecta are too small relative to their parent bodies to yield pairs of pairs of closely bound, similarly sized bodies (Durda, 1995).

Both the second and third mechanisms, however, are plausible sources of contact binaries. The geometry for grazing impacts is difficult to achieve, and has only been explicitly invoked in the case of one object, the dwarf planet Haumea (Leinhardt et al, 2009). However, rotational fission produced by grazing impacts easily yields gravitationally bound rubble piles which would be in close enough proximity to be near or in contact with one another (Descamps and Marchis, 2008). Catastrophic collisions are even more likely to produce contact binaries than grazing impacts. Three sets of numerical simulations performed by Durda (1995) showed that catastrophic collisions not only produce large numbers of gravitationally bound binaries, they also preferentially form contact structures.

As discussed in section 1.1.3.4, it is difficult to place strict limits on how frequent collisions are in the Kuiper Belt today. However, the total mass of objects in the dense, dynamically active debris disk which formed beyond the giant planets in the early Solar System was hundreds or thousands of times greater than that of the Kuiper Belt today (see section 1.1.2). At that time, the Solar System as a whole was also far less dynamically stable (Gladman et al, 2001; Gomes et al, 2005). Such conditions would have promoted collisions, both grazing and catastrophic, which could have produced contact binaries.

1.2.1.3 Tidal Effects

An object need not be directly impacted by another body in order to be affected by it. Tidal effects play a significant role in disrupting comets and asteroids in the inner Solar System. Tidal forces could have been similarly prominent effect on planetesimals which formed in the outer primordial Solar System, beyond the giant planets.

There are two ways in which tidal forces can cause the fragmentation of small bodies:

The first of the two is brute-force disruption occurring when a minor planet passes within a larger body’s Roche Limit. This phenomenon was famously observed in 1992, when the comet Shoemaker-Levy 9 was torn apart during a close approach to Jupiter, shown in figure 6. Asteroids and comets are particularly susceptible to tidal disruption because they are typically rubble piles with negligible

tensile strength to counteract tidal disruption (Asphaug and Benz, 1999).

Nevertheless, a planet-sized body is required to exert tidal forces of sufficient magnitude to disrupt even a relatively small body. Previous studies (e.g. Moshovitz et al, 2015) have speculated that the moons of gas giant planets may have experienced complete tidal disruption and reformation during the early Solar System, and it is possible that the same process could have occurred during interactions between primordial planetesimals and Neptune during giant planet migration. However, the precise likelihood of such a chance encounter between Neptune and a planetesimal during that period has never been definitively assessed.

Figure 6: A composite of Hubble Space Telescope images of the comet Shoemaker-Levy 9. Shoemaker-Levy 9 passed within the Roche Limit of Jupiter, experiencing tidal forces which entirely disrupted it. A similar process, acting via interactions with Neptune, could have disrupted minor planets in the primordial trans-Neptunian debris disk, but is unlikely to have led to binaries that were dynamically stable in the long term (Credit: NASA/STSCI).

A far more stable means by which tidal interactions can break apart minor planets is through tidal spin-up. This occurs when an object experiences tidal effects which are insufficient to entirely disrupt it, but are able to impart a significant amount of additional angular momentum.

Scheeres et al (2000) show that the total increase in angular momentum ΔH that occurs during a planetary flyby is

$$\Delta H = \int_{t_0}^{\infty} H dt \quad (1)$$

Where t_0 is the initial time of interaction and

$$\dot{H} = -\frac{M_1 M_2}{M_1 + M_2} \dot{G} \quad (2)$$

and \dot{G} is the specific orbit angular momentum of the system with the vector decomposition

$$\dot{G} = G \begin{bmatrix} \sin i \sin \Omega \\ -\sin i \cos \Omega \\ \cos i \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

for orbital inclination i and angular velocity vector Ω .

Walsh and Richardson (2006) did extensive numerical simulations of this mechanism. They found that rotational fission of the simulated objects was a frequent outcome, with approximately 4.5% of encounters resulting in the formation of a binary. Binary formation was more likely in cases where the disrupted object was low mass (50% more likely) rapidly spinning to begin with were (50%), or highly elongated (30% more likely for a semimajor axis ratio of 2). Decreasing the encounter velocity between the two objects also led to the formation of more binaries by a factor of up to 60%. Separation between the primary and secondary varied from 0 to 1000 R_{pri} , peaking at 5 R_{pri} , and approximately 3% of encounters produced contact binaries. That study was focused on reproducing the observed fraction of binaries in the NEA population because NEAs frequently closely approach the inner planets. However, the simulation could equivalently apply to tidal interactions in the trans-Neptunian region, particularly when they were more common in the primordial Solar System.

Figure 7: A simulation of tidal disruption in which an asteroid, following a close approach to a larger body, is tidally spun up, experiences rotational fission, and re-forms into a binary, drawn from Walsh and Richardson (2005). This is a likely process through which stable binaries could have formed in the primordial Solar System beyond Neptune.

1.2.1.4 Mergers Via Dynamical Friction

Another merger mechanism, discussed by Goldreich et al (2002) is that of previously distinct bodies encountering one another during runaway accretion in the early Solar System, when the number density of objects in the Kuiper Belt, and throughout the Solar System, was orders of magnitude larger.

Goldreich et al (2002) propose that during runaway accretion large KBOs penetrate one another's gravitational spheres of influence (or Hill spheres) at a rate of approximately 10^{-4} y^{-1} per large body. When this occurs, the pair is known as

a transient binary until it either becomes gravitationally bound or breaks apart. They then propose two mechanisms by which a transient binary could become bound due after losing kinetic energy in gravitational exchanges with nearby objects (a process called dynamical friction). In the first, dynamical friction with small bodies passing through the binary’s Hill sphere results in a fractional energy loss of 0.03 during each solar orbital period, causing half of transient binaries to remain permanently gravitationally bound. The second process relies on a third large body entering the transient binary’s Hill sphere. This object exerts sufficient dynamical friction on the pair that they no longer have sufficient kinetic energy to separate, leaving the original pair permanently bound. Via numerical simulations, Goldreich et al (2002) found that these two processes yielded permanent binaries at rates of 310^{-6} y^{-1} and 310^{-7} y^{-1} per large body, respectively. This yields a present-day binary abundance which is highly dependent on the number of primordial objects which were not ejected from the outer Solar System during its early period of instability.

As mentioned in section 1.1.2, the exact number density of objects in the Kuiper Belt during formation is not known. However, it is known to be higher by orders of magnitude than it is today, and so the process of energy loss to dynamical friction would not have ceased once the transient binary has become permanently bound (Gomes et al, 2005; Goldreich et al, 2002). The inspiral which bound the two objects to begin with would continue during gravitational interactions with nearby small objects, causing the orbital separation of the pair to steadily decrease.

Goldreich et al (2002) estimated that binaries formed in the Kuiper Belt with mass ratios near unity would achieve contact on a timescale of approximately 10^6 y. This process could help to explain the genesis of contact binary asteroids whose component parts originated from different parent bodies, such as 25143 Itokawa (Hirabayashi et al, 2008) As this process yields large numbers of contact binaries without requiring numerous collisions or radiative effects, it seems a promising source of many present-day Kuiper Belt contact binaries.

1.2.1.5 Born Binaries

One final possibility is that some objects could simply be born as extremely high angular momentum rubble piles. This theory owes much to the work of Johansen and Lacerda (2010) explaining the preferential prograde rotation of Solar System bodies. While most small ($d < 1$ km-scale) objects in the Solar System rotate in collisionally randomized orientations, larger bodies, particularly those with $R > 150$ km, are thought to retain their primordial obliquities. The overwhelming majority of such objects are rotating prograde, with the exceptions of Venus and Neptune. Since the former’s rotation can be explained by extreme atmospheric

solar tides (Correia et al, 2003) and the latter’s by an impact (Slattery et al, 1991), bodies forming out of the solar nebula must have done so preferentially rotating prograde.

Johansen and Lacerda (2010) explain this phenomenon by examining the rotational effects of accretion from circumplanetary discs onto evolving protoplanets. In several numerical simulations of such a scenario, they found that the accretion of centimeter- to meter-scale particles from a surrounding disc systematically increased objects’ prograde rotation. In some cases, particularly in regions where solid-to-gas ratios were at or greater than unity, this mechanism was powerful enough to bring about rotational fission of the protoplanet, which could subsequently lead to the formation of a close binary out of the rubble. While it is difficult to make quantitative predictions of the impact of this effect on the present-day Kuiper Belt binary population. This appears to be a plausible mechanism for forming KBO binaries. Furthermore, the reliance of this process on a moderately high solid-to-gas ratio suggests that it would be most pronounced in the midplane of protoplanetary disks, corresponding to the ecliptic plane. If we assume that many Kuiper Belt binaries are indeed primordial in nature, this could in turn play a part in explaining the particularly high incidence of Kuiper Belt binaries at low inclinations. However, no research has been done on the rate at which this process forms contact binaries as opposed to wide binaries.

1.2.2 Contact Binary Lightcurve Characteristics

Contact binaries are typically small objects (ranging from order $d = 1$ among NEAs to order $d = 100$ in the Kuiper Belt) as contact binaries are not stable configurations among objects large enough to be in hydrostatic equilibrium (Benner, 2015; Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004). As a result, they are found exclusively among the asteroid, comet, and trans-Neptunian object populations, and it is not possible to directly image any but a few NEAs at high enough resolution to confirm their binary status. This has been done by spacecraft (1.2) and on occasion by ground-based radar in the case of NEAs such as 1999 JD6 (NRAO, 2015). However, the only way to detect the presence of a contact binary at great distances is to perform differential photometry and obtain a lightcurve.

No object is a perfectly uniform sphere, not least the 1- to 100-km-scale rubble piles found in the trans-Neptunian region. As such, lightcurves will show variations in brightness as objects rotate. These are often used to model the rotational period and general shape of minor planets. A typical asteroid or trans-Neptunian object will show variations of at most a few tenths of a magnitude.

Contact binaries are most easily distinguished by observing extreme magnitude variation Δm in an object’s lightcurve. While contact binaries may show a range of Δm from 0 to ≈ 1.2 (Lacerda, 2011), they can only be confidently identified in

cases of large Δm and two other causes can be ruled out:

1. *Albedo variation*: Just four Solar System objects greater than 25 km across have been found to show $\Delta m > 1.0$ mag. One is the Saturnian moon Iapetus (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004). In Iapetus' case, this is due to enormous albedo variation across the moon's surface. Iapetus is unusual in that it is tidally locked and its leading hemisphere has been significantly darkened by the deposition of ring material and of ejecta from more distant moons (most notably Phoebe). This, in turn, has fueled a feedback effect where the darker hemisphere absorbs significantly more heat, fueling the sublimation of high-albedo ices and further darkening that region of the as low-albedo rocks and dust (so-called "sublimation lag") are left behind (Cook and Franklin, 1970). In the absence of a similar phenomenon which could cause significant darkening of one hemisphere, there are no known mechanisms which could cause such extreme albedo variation across the surface of a single body.
2. *Aspherical shape*: A highly elongated object will also show wide variation in brightness Δm as it rotates, as the surface area visible to the observer will vary depending on the object's viewing geometry:

$$\Delta m = 2.5 \log_{10} (a/b), \quad (4)$$

describes the relation between magnitude variation and dimensions of a tri-axial ellipsoid viewed equatorially, where Δm is expressed in magnitudes and a and b are two of the semiaxes (with the object rotating around the third axis, c). This effect has previously cited as an explanation for the lightcurves of asteroids 216 Kleopatra ($\Delta m = 1.18$, $a/b = 2.3$) and 624 Hektor ($\Delta m = 1.10$, $a/b = 2.0$), as they are thought to be highly elongated due to rotational deformation (Leone et al. 1984; Hestroffer et al. 2002; Washabaugh and Scheeres 2002). Most 10- to 100-km sized bodies have little to no tensile strength and are held together entirely by their own self-gravity. There will be a period T_{crit} (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004) at which centripetal acceleration is equal to gravitational acceleration toward the center of the body:

$$T_{crit} = \frac{3\pi^{1/2}}{G\rho} \quad (5)$$

The limiting equilibrium shapes of rotating strengthless fluid bodies were given by Chandrasekhar (1987) and are discussed in section 4.2. The maximum photometric range of a rotational ellipsoid rotating at T_{crit} should be

$\Delta m \approx 0.9$ (Leone et al, 1984), corresponding to an axis ratio a/b of 2.3. Greater magnitude variations require additional tensile strength above self-gravity, else they would simply pull themselves apart.

Objects with $\Delta m > 0.9$ mag that have no evident mechanism for producing a hemispheric discrepancy in albedo, then, are likely to be contact binaries. Shepard and Jewitt (2004) suggest that this is the most likely cause of 216 Kleopatra and 624 Hektor's large Δm , and radar images of 216 Kleopatra are also indicative of it being a contact binary (Ostro et al. 2000). This is discussed in greater detail in section 2.1 in the context of the identification of the KBO 2001 QG₂₉₈ as a contact binary.

2 The Contact Binary 2001 QG₂₉₈

The remainder of this work is dedicated to laying out our method for modeling and fitting the lightcurves of Kuiper Belt contact binaries. In this chapter, we discuss the discovery and identification of the only known Kuiper Belt contact binary, 2001 QG₂₉₈, as well as previous efforts to fit and characterize its lightcurve. In chapter 3, we discuss our own attempts to gather additional data on 2001 QG₂₉₈. In chapter 4 generate a library of physical contact binary models. In chapter 5 we simulate lightcurves of each model binary. In chapter 6 we perform χ^2 fits to two lightcurves of 2001 QG₂₉₈ and discuss the accuracy of our model. Finally, in chapter 7 we provide a summary of this work and discuss future directions in which it could be taken.

2.1 Identification as a Contact Binary

The KBO 2001 QG₂₉₈ is a typical “Plutino” resonant KBO orbiting in Neptune’s 3:2 MMR at $a = 39.2$ AU, $e = 0.19$, and $i = 6.5^\circ$. It was first observed in depth by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) using the University of Hawaii 2.2-meter and Keck telescopes located on Mauna Kea. These observations were performed as part of the Hawaii Kuiper Belt Variability Project (HKBVP; see Jewitt and Sheppard 2002; Sheppard and Jewitt 2002, 2004). HKBVP investigated the period and shape of bright KBOs. Of the 34 objects observed as part of that project, it was found to display an exceptionally large variation in brightness of approximately 1.14 magnitudes. 2001 QG₂₉₈ also an unusually long period of 13.7744 hours.

This extreme variability of 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve makes it the last of the four known Solar System objects with diameter greater than 25 km whose lightcurve covers a range greater than 1.0 mag (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004). Since the Kuiper Belt has no similar mechanism to Saturn’s moon and ring system to cause significant deposition of infalling material (and since, even if it did, it would end up evenly distributed across 2001 QG₂₉₈’s rotating surface), albedo variation cannot provide a sufficient explanation for this high Δm . Furthermore, equation 4 (see section 1.2.2) yields an implausibly high lower limit to a/b of 2.81. Such a large aspect ratio would quickly lead to the object flying apart due to centripetal force. Hence 2001 QG₂₉₈’s magnitude variation cannot be explained solely by rotational deformation (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004).

Instead, Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) posited that the most likely explanation for 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve was that the object was a contact or near-contact binary, each of whose component parts were highly tidally elongated. 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve is not consistent with that of a *wide* binary, as its brightness smoothly fluctuates over the course of its rotation rather than featuring abrupt dips in bright-

Figure 8: The extreme Δm of resonant KBO 2001 QG₂₉₈. The object’s lightcurve is shown in figure 8a, on the left. These data were compiled from observations made by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and phase-folded to a period of 13.7744 hours. The data are repeated an extra half period for clarity. A plot comparing Δm and rotation frequency for several large asteroids and KBOs is shown on in figure 8, on the right (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004). Objects in region A have lightcurves explained equally well by elongation, albedo variation, or binarity. Objects in region C have lightcurves best explained by rotational elongation. Objects in region C are likely binaries. The extreme range of apparent magnitudes seen in 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve makes it one of only four >25-km bodies in the Solar System to vary in brightness by greater than 1.0 mag. As explained by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004), this implies that the object is actually a contact binary.

ness during each eclipse. Rotation of a wide binary with the observed period of 13.7744 hours would require an implausibly large bulk density (thousands of kg m^{-3}). Modeling 2001 QG₂₉₈ as a close binary made up of equal spheres would not generate a sufficiently large magnitude variation. However, two essentially strengthless objects in such close proximity would produce significant tidal deformation upon one another, leading to a pair of tidally locked, elongated objects (Leone et al, 1984), as in figure 9. Accounting for the component parts of the binary as Roche ellipsoids rather than spheres puts a significantly higher ceiling on Δm of approximately 1.2 mag. As such, Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) argued that a contact binary consisting of tidally elongated ellipsoids was the most plausible explanation for 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve. The same model can account for the $\Delta m > 1.0$ variations of asteroids 624 Hektor (Hartmann and Cruikshank 1978; Weidenschilling 1980; Leone et al. 1984) and 216 Kleopatra (Leone et al. 1984; Ostro et al. 2000; Hestroffer et al. 2002; Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004).

Figure 9: A model contact binary consisting of two tidally distorted ellipsoids illuminated face-on. The color scale from red to blue corresponds to increasing surface brightness. Note that both objects have been significantly elongated along an axis pointing through the binary’s center of mass, and that the less massive of the two is significantly more ellipsoidal than its partner.

2.2 A Change in the Lightcurve of 2001 QG₂₉₈

In 2010, Lacerda (2011) performed additional photometric time series observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈ using the 2.9-meter Isaac Newton telescope at La Palma, constructing the first new lightcurve since Sheppard and Jewitt’s (2004). This newer lightcurve (figure 10) aligned perfectly with the 2003 data, confirming the period of 13.774 hours found in Sheppard and Jewitt (2004). However, while the lightcurve’s *maxima* fell within 0.1 mag of what was predicted based on the object’s progression in its orbit, but the lightcurve’s *minima* rose substantially. Compared to $\Delta m = 1.14$ in 2004, the 2010 data displayed $\Delta m \approx 0.7$.

Lacerda explained this change as being the result of a change in viewing geometry between 2003 and 2010. In 2003, 2001 QG₂₉₈ was likely positioned relative to Earth such that the aspect angle (defined as the angle between the rotational axis of the object and a line between it and the observer) was at or near 90 degrees (see figure 12). The aspect angle could have changed by as much as 16 degrees between 2003 and 2010 depending on the obliquity (or axial tilt) of the system. In a zero-obliquity system, with 2001 QG₂₉₈ rotating exactly in the orbital plane,

Figure 10: Lightcurves of 2001 QG₂₉₈. Data taken in 2003 by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) are shown in red, while those taken in 2010 by Lacerda (2011) are shown in blue. The data are repeated an extra half period for clarity. Over that eight-year span, the magnitude variation seen in photometry of 2001 QG₂₉₈ decreased significantly: Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) observed a Δm of 1.14 mag, while Lacerda (2011) observed a Δm of 0.7 mag.

this would simply manifest as a slight phase shift in the lightcurve without change in Δm .

The higher the system's obliquity, the more its lightcurve will change as it progresses in its orbit. Figures 13 and 14 show this phenomenon, wherein this change in viewing geometry causes the binary to go from fully eclipsing to only partially eclipsing at a phase angle of $\phi = 180$. In the extreme case of a 90-degree inclined binary, its aspect angle would decrease by 2.29° per year (a rate dictated by its orbital period). This would cause its lightcurve to go from the extreme variation seen in 2003 when it was at or near an aspect angle of 90 degrees to a nearly featureless lightcurve when, a quarter-orbit later, it is at an aspect angle of zero degrees. The relevant geometry to this theory is shown in figure 12. If this geometry applies to 2001 QG₂₉₈, we should expect to see the Δm in 2001 QG₂₉₈'s lightcurve steadily decrease along with its aspect angle in observations after 2010.

As discussed in section 2.1, 2001 QG₂₉₈ was only identified as a contact binary because of the extreme variation in its lightcurve. However, after only seven years

Figure 11: Predicted change in Δm as 2001 QG₂₉₈ progresses in its orbit, based on a number of different possible obliquities ϵ (Lacerda, 2011). The gray circles correspond to the Δm of 2001 QG₂₉₈ in 2003 and in 2010. At higher obliquities, Δm should decrease more sharply with time.

(less than 5% of 2001 QG₂₉₈'s orbital period), this variation had decreased to 0.7 mag. Had 2001 QG₂₉₈ only been observed in 2010 and not in 2003, the object would have been incorrectly identified as that of a rotational ellipsoid or other highly asymmetrical object rather than as a contact binary.

The implications of this long-term variability in contact binary lightcurves of KBOs is highly significant. Numerous KBOs in the Hawaii Kuiper Belt Variability Project showed large Δm that was insufficient to classify them as contact binaries rather than rotational ellipsoids (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004; see figure 8b). However, the evolution in the lightcurve of 2001 QG₂₉₈ demonstrates that some fraction of those objects may have been contact binaries at a point in their orbit with unfavorable viewing geometry that prevented Earth-based observers from seeing their maximal range of brightness variation.

There may well be objects previously identified as rotational ellipsoids that, with follow-up observations, would show $\Delta m > 1.0$, implying that they are contact binaries. That the fraction of contact binaries in the Kuiper Belt may be higher than previously thought (Lacerda, 2011).

Figure 12: Diagram of various 2001 QG₂₉₈ viewing geometries in 2003 and 2010, drawn from Lacerda (2011). The object’s orbit lies within the shaded plane (labeled as such). Earth is located at the black dot in the rightmost corner, and lines of sight in 2003 and 2010 are shown by the two dashed black lines (labeled “LOS₂₀₀₃” and “LOS₂₀₁₀”). In that seven-year span, 2001 QG₂₉₈ has advanced 16 degrees in its orbit, as shown. Possible rotational axes of 2001 QG₂₉₈ are shown by the colored solid arrows (with observationally indistinguishable counterparts to each represented by dotted arrows of the same color). Note that, regardless of the orientation of 2001 QG₂₉₈’s axis in 2003, the aspect angle (defined as the angle between the line of sight and the rotational axis) is 90 degrees. However, different rotational axes correspond to very different aspect angles in 2010. This is likely to be the cause of the object’s changing lightcurve over that same timespan.

Figure 13: A contact binary shown on the plane of the sky through a full period of rotation. The binary is viewed at an obliquity of 90 degrees and aspect angle of 90 degrees, analogous to 2001 QG₂₉₈ in 2003. m_{max} occurs at $\phi = 0$, and m_{min} occurs at $\phi = 180$. Note that the smaller component of the binary is completely obscured at a phase angle of 180 degrees.

36

Figure 14: A contact binary shown on the plane of the sky through a full period of rotation. The binary is viewed at an obliquity of 90 degrees and aspect angle of 74 degrees, analogous to 2001 QG₂₉₈ in 2010. m_{max} occurs at $\phi = 0$, and m_{min} occurs at $\phi = 180$. Note that the smaller component of the binary is no longer completely obscured at a phase angle of 180 degrees, leading to a diminished Δm .

3 Observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈

3.1 Post-2010 Pan-STARRS Observations

The Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System (hereafter referred to as “Pan-STARRS”) survey has been active since 2010. 25 Pan-STARRS fields included 2001 QG₂₉₈ between 2010 and 2013. and the resultant photometric data, folded to a period of 13.774 hours, are shown in figure 15. Pan-STARRS performed many of these observations in the i and w filters, while the observations performed by both Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and Lacerda (2011) were in the r filter. Since no w-r or r-i colors are known for 2001 QG₂₉₈, we applied color-corrections to the i- and w-filter Pan-STARRS data using theoretical mean asteroid colors determined by Fitzsimmons (2011). These w-r and r-i colors were calculated by multiplying the solar spectrum by the mean C-class spectrum provided by DeMeo et al (2009) and should serve as a reasonable predictor of the color of 2001 QG₂₉₈.

Figure 15: Period-folded lightcurve of 2001 QG₂₉₈, compiling data drawn from Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) (red circles), Lacerda (2011) (blue circles) and Pan-STARRS observations in 2010, 2011, 2012, and 2013. While the Pan-STARRS data taken in 2010 are clearly inconsistent with both the 2003 Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and 2010 Lacerda (2011) data, we feel confident that they can be disregarded due to the undeveloped state of the Pan-STARRS photometric data pipeline at that time. While the remaining data does line up relatively well with past observations, and the data points from 2012 are suggestive of the decreasing magnitude range seen in Lacerda (2011), the error bars on all Pan-STARRS data are too large to support any definitive conclusion.

As can be seen in figure 15, the Pan-STARRS observations from 2011, 2012, and 2013 all correspond reasonably well with the data taken in 2003 and 2010 by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and Lacerda (2011), respectively. However, the Pan-STARRS data taken in 2010 are notable outliers. None of the points closely overlap with prior observations at the same rotational phase. While this initially might be cause for concern, it is likely due to the relative infancy of the Pan-STARRS data reduction pipeline in 2010. Since these data were among the first produced by Pan-STARRS, its photometry was not as well-calibrated and refined as it has since become. As a result, we do not believe these data points to be representative of the actual brightness of 2001 QG₂₉₈ at that time, and are comfortable disregarding them as outliers produced by errors in data reduction. Correlating Pan-STARRS data against data on well-studied objects—including the results of prior observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈ (as well as upcoming observations, discussed in section 3.2) has played a valuable role in highlighting the deficiencies of early Pan-STARRS data reduction, allowing for the pipeline to be updated and improved (Magnier, 2006; Chambers, 2011).

Unfortunately, despite corresponding far better with prior observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈, the latter three years of Pan-STARRS observations do little to support or challenge Lacerda (2011)’s suggestion regarding the way in which 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve is evolving as a function of its progress through its orbit. While the 2011-2013 data are suggestive of a decreasing Δm as Lacerda (2011) predicted (see figure 11), the error bars on those points are too large to be useful in refining our understanding of the long-term behavior of 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve, or even in establishing an upper limit in Δm since 2010. Further observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈ are necessary to verify the trend in decreasing magnitude range.

3.2 Follow-Up Observations

Follow-up observations were made to measure the magnitude range of 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve. These data were initially collected using the KeplerCam CCD on the 1.2 meter telescope located at the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory (FLWO) at Mt. Hopkins, AZ¹ (Szentgyorgyi et al, 2005). For all observations we took 600-second exposures in the i filter, as it is capable of deeper observations and better general performance during long exposures than the r filter. The resulting photometry was then corrected to r magnitude in the same manner as the Pan-STARRS data (see section 3.1). Since the KeplerCam CCD consists of four readouts with separate amplifiers which are then stitched together to form a single image, we performed initial observations with the target centered in the second (top left) amplifier. However, due to severe fringing (see figure 17) around the

¹<http://www.sao.arizona.edu/FLWO/whipple.html>

periphery of the image, we later relocated it to the center of the entire stitched frame.

Figure 16: Lightcurve of 2001 QG₂₉₈ showing the phase coverage of planned observations on the nights of 2015 December 12-13 (red), 13-14 (yellow), 14-15 (green), 18-19 (blue), and 20-21 (purple) and January 11-12 (orange) and 16-17 (brown). The nights of December 13-14 and 18-19 and of January 16-17 are shifted by a full rotation for visual clarity. These nights were scheduled to provide excellent coverage of the entire rotational phase of 2001 QG₂₉₈, and had they yielded usable data would have helped to further refine the overall trend in reduced magnitude range seen by Lacerda (2011).

Telescope time was scheduled on the 1.2-meter for the nights of 2015 December 12-13, 13-14, 14-15, 18-19, and 20-21 and 2016 January 11-12 and 16-17. For each night, we determined the maximum amount of time that was not currently devoted to other transit observations and at which the airmass of 2001 QG₂₉₈ was below 2.0, and ensured that the Moon was not prohibitively close ($< 10^\circ$ angular separation) to 2001 QG₂₉₈ in the sky (which was the case for an earlier planned night of observations). These nights were intended to cover the bulk of an entire rotational phase of 2001 QG₂₉₈, as shown in figure 16, and would have helped to further investigate the trend observed by Lacerda (2011). If the decrease in Δm seen in the 2010 observations is due to a steady change in the viewing geometry of the 2001 QG₂₉₈ as it continues in its orbit, then contemporary observations should see a further decrease in Δm from the value of 0.7 mag. observed in 2010 to $\Delta m \approx 0.5$ in 2015.

Unfortunately, the winter of 2015-2016 featured consistently poor weather and

seeing conditions. Through the scheduled nights in December, as well as several more in early- to mid-January, we were consistently faced with clouds, precipitation, and occasional technical difficulties. On the nights that we were able to take data, seeing conditions were not adequate to reliably detect an object as faint as 2001 QG₂₉₈ ($r \approx 22$), which is at the edge of the 1.2-meter telescope’s observing capabilities in good conditions. Despite 20 hours of scheduled time, we were unable to obtain any useful data from our observations.

Figure 17: A fully flatfielded and bias-subtracted image taken by the Whipple 1.2-meter telescope showing peripheral fringing typical of all images we obtained using KeplerCam. We initially positioned our target in the center of the top left quadrant (the center of Amp 2). Because of fringing similar to that seen here, we were unable to obtain useful data from several nights’ observations.

We performed one set of additional observations using the PRISM instrument on the Perkins 72” (1.8-meter) telescope, located at Lowell Observatory in Flagstaff, AZ. We received four hours of telescope time in total, during which we performed 600-second exposures in the r filter. The signal to noise of these data was significantly higher than what we were able to achieve with the Mt. Hopkins 1.2-meter telescope. However, since these observations had to be fit around an already tight observing schedule, they fell in an uninformative region of 2001 QG₂₉₈’s rotational phase ($0.0 < \phi < 0.2$). These data are discussed at greater length in section 3.7.

3.3 Reduction of Raw Data

The data from 2003, 2010, and 2010-2013 provided by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004), Lacerda (2011), and the Pan-STARRS survey was fully reduced. The data taken using the FLWO 1.2-meter telescope and Lowell Observatory Perkins 72" telescope had to be corrected for bias and flatfielded before we could perform photometry. Bias frames are zero-exposure-time “images” which are median-combined and subtracted from all science frames to eliminate noise involved in converting the CCD readout to an image. Flatfields are exposures of the uniformly illuminated (“flat”) sky at twilight. All science frames are then divided by the combined flatfield in order to eliminate variation in sensitivity across the CCD, often due to the presence of grains of dust or other material. The 2015 December 30th data from Lowell Observatory were reduced using 20 bias frames and 20 r filter twilight flats in IRAF (Tody, 1986) and DS9 (SAO, 2000) using Perkins/PRISM reduction guidelines written by Dr. Phil Massey (personal communication, July 22, 2015). Reduction of Mt. Hopkins 1.2-meter data was carried out using procedures outlined in Carter et al. (2011), which uses standard IDL routines.

3.4 Photometry

Following data reduction, relative photometry was performed on all science frames from both the Lowell Observatory Perkins 72" and the Whipple Observatory 1.2-meter telescopes. We performed photometry on both data taken at Mt. Hopkins and the December 30th data from Lowell Observatory in *AstroImageJ*, a general-purpose astronomy image processing suite developed by Karen Collins at the University of Louisville (Collins and Kielkopf, 2013).

For each night of data, we first performed a plate solution to eliminate any small inconsistencies in sky position from one image to the next which may have occurred due to guiding errors.

We then identified the target when it was possible to do so (see below) using finding charts generated by the NASA Skyview website².

We then performed aperture photometry on the target, using five bright, well-resolved stars as comparisons. As part of its aperture photometry package, *AstroImageJ* automatically averages sky counts in the surrounding area (sampling from a user-defined annulus, which we ensured was clear of stars or other background objects) and subtracts them from the counts measured on the target and comparisons.

For both the target and comparison stars in each frame, *AstroImageJ* calculates an error ϵ using the error equation for CCD data given by Merline and Howell

²<http://skyview.gsfc.nasa.gov/current/cgi/titlepage.pl>

(1995):

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sqrt{N_*G + n_{pix}(1.0 + \frac{n_{pix}}{n_B})(N_SG + N_D + N_R^2 + G^2\sigma_f^2)}}{G} \quad (6)$$

where N_* is the total integrated counts from the source, N_S is the average sky counts per pixel, N_D is the dark counts per pixel (read from the FITS header), N_R is the CCD read noise, G is the gain, n_{pix} is the number of pixels within the source aperture, and n_{sky} is the number of pixels within the sky background annulus. σ_f is the uncertainty in the mean of the distribution of the signal from the fractional count in a single pixel. *AstroImageJ* automatically uses the value of σ_f for well-resolved sources, which is equal to $\sqrt{1/12}$ (Merline and Howell, 1995).

For the 2015 December 30 data from Lowell Observatory 2001 QG₂₉₈, while faint, was readily visible and easily measured using *AstroImageJ*'s aperture photometry tools.

However, 2001 QG₂₉₈ was prohibitively faint in even the best data from the FLWO 1.2-meter telescope. It was only barely visible in the data from January 28, which provided the best seeing conditions of any night; however, photometry using *AstroImageJ* and numerous other photometric tools failed. As such, none of the data collected using the FLWO 1.2-meter telescope was usable.

The difference in detection signal to noise between the Lowell Observatory 72" Perkins data and the FLWO 1.2-meter data is evident in figure 18.

3.5 Conversion from Apparent to Absolute Magnitude

In order to determine the intrinsic brightness of a Solar System object, its absolute magnitude is calculated as the magnitude it would have if observed with a phase angle (α) of 0° at heliocentric (Δ) and geocentric (R) distances of 1 AU. While this is obviously a physically impossible measurement to make in reality, controlling for the effects of variations in α , Δ , and R is useful for theoretical comparisons of one object to another. This conversion was performed in anticipation of comparing existing lightcurves of 2001 QG₂₉₈ to future data on that and other objects. We derived all absolute magnitude values from apparent magnitudes in the r band, which necessitated converting b and v magnitudes to r . This could be done simply by subtracting the $v - r$ color from v magnitudes, and subtracting both the $b - v$ and $v - r$ colors from b magnitudes. In the case of 2001 QG₂₉₈, these values were 1.00 ± 0.04 and 0.60 ± 0.02 , respectively. Once all apparent magnitudes had been converted to r -band, the following equation was used to convert to absolute magnitude:

$$m_R(1, 1, 0) = m_R - 5\log(R\Delta) - \beta\alpha \quad (7)$$

Figure 18: 2001 QG₂₉₈, observed using the Lowell Observatory 72” Perkins (left, from December 30, 2015) and Whipple Observatory 1.2-meter (right, from January 28, 2016) telescopes (between the two observations, 2001 QG₂₉₈ had moved 11’ on the sky, so the background stars in each image are different). Both images are fully bias-subtracted and flatfielded, and were taken at comparable airmass. In both images, the target is centered in the bullseye; however, while it is easily visible (if somewhat faint) in the Perkins image, it is almost entirely invisible in the 1.2-meter image. No images taken using the 1.2-meter exceeded this detection quality.

where m_R is the apparent red magnitude of the object and β is the phase function, assumed to be $0.16 \text{ mag deg}^{-1}$ as is typical for KBOs at low phase angles (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2004).

3.6 Determination of Period and Phase Folding

The period of 2001 QG₂₉₈ was determined using Phase Dispersion Minimization (PDM; Stellingworth, 1978), which measures the variance of unphased time and magnitude data divided by its variance when folded over a given period. This value is known as the Θ -parameter; $\Theta \ll 1$ for a given period suggests that it is a good fit for the data. The code we used was the the PyPDM class, from the PyAstronomy package³. Running PDM on the observational data of 2001 QG₂₉₈ showed extremely low Θ values for 6.887 hours and 13.774 hours, as shown in figure 20. This agrees exactly with the results of Sheppard and Jewitt (2004). While Θ is

³<http://www.hs.uni-hamburg.de/DE/Ins/Per/Czesla/PyA/PyA/index.html>

Figure 19: A lightcurve of the KBO 2001 QG₂₉₈, compiled from observations made by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and phase-folded to a period of 13.7744 hours. This is the same data shown in figure 8, with apparent magnitudes now converted to absolute magnitudes using equation 7. The conversion to absolute magnitude smooths some the small scatter around the overall periodic trend seen in figure 8.

Figure 20: Phase dispersion minimization (PDM) plot of Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈. Periods which correspond to low values of theta are the most likely to fit the actual data. The lowest peak is at 6.8872 hours, and the second-lowest at 13.8874 hours. These period correspond to a half rotation and full rotation of the 2001 QG₂₉₈ contact binary, respectively.

lower for 6.887 hours than for 13.774, we draw the same conclusion as Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) that the actual period must be double that, since a rotating contact binary will display two dips in brightness corresponding to different orientations. Having established the object’s period, our data was then phased by each of these periods to yield a single-peaked lightcurve (with a period of 6.887 hours) and a double-peaked lightcurve (with a period of 13.774 hours).

3.7 Observational Results

Our observations at Lowell Observatory were of excellent photometric quality, with an RMS scatter of less than 0.01 mag. Unfortunately, they were almost exactly centered around one of the maxima of 2001 QG₂₉₈’s lightcurve. These data are shown, along with those drawn from Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and Lacerda (2011), in figure 21. Without phase coverage of either of the dips in the object’s lightcurve, we were not able to gather any new information about how its Δm changed in the time since the observations of Lacerda (2011). We are thus wholly reliant on archival data to test and validate the method of physical modeling that was the focus of this project.

Figure 21: Lightcurve of 2001 QG₂₉₈ showing data collected using the 72” Perkins telescope at Lowell Observatory plotted with the data taken in 2003 by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and in 2010 by Lacerda (2011). While the signal-to-noise of these new data was sufficiently high for useful analysis, the points are clustered around the $0 < \phi < 0.2$ maximum, and do not provide any phase coverage of either eclipse. As such, they do not offer any additional information about how 2001 QG₂₉₈’s Δm may have changed since it was last observed.

4 The Challenge of Modeling Contact Binaries

The problem of constructing physical models of contact- and near-contact binaries is a complex one. Our goal is to create a model which can produce a realistic lightcurve of any theoretical contact binary, and from which physical properties can be inferred. Any such model must account for several parameters, including:

1. *Relative dimensions of each component body:* This can be done with varying degrees of complexity, ranging from paired spheres (e.g. Wijesinghe and Tedesco, 1979) to ellipsoids (e.g. Lacerda, 2011) to more complex tidally deformed shapes (e.g. Gnat and Sari, 2010). Throughout this paper we will use a , b , and c to refer to the three semiaxes of ellipsoidal objects, with a always being the longest axis. In cases where we are dealing with paired ellipsoids, we use A , B , and C to refer to the semiaxes of the larger object (the “primary”) and a , b , and c to refer to the semiaxes of the smaller object (the “secondary”).
2. *Densities of each component body:* While it is possible to model each object as having a different composition (as is needed for Itokawa), most studies assume constant density for the entire binary (e.g. Lacerda, 2011). From the density and dimensions, mass can then be inferred. Throughout this paper ρ is used to refer to density, and q is used to refer to the mass ratio between the two component objects of a binary.
3. *Orbital separation:* This can be calculated (assuming Keplerian rotation) using the derived masses of the objects and the observed orbital period.
4. *Illuminated area and viewing geometry of each object:* This is a function of the projected (two-dimensional) area of each object relative to the sun at each point in its orbit, as well as any visual overlap (if any) which leaves part of one of the two objects in shadow. It must then be determined how much of the illuminated area of each object is visible to the observer, accounting for (a) phase angle, (b) physical orientation, and (c) projected overlap of the pair. For spherical models, this question is addressed in section 4.1, while for ellipsoid models it is addressed in section 4.2.
5. *Reflectance properties:* The amount of light reflected as a function of area depends on the surface properties of the object. For high-albedo (icy) surfaces, the Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function is used, while for low-albedo (rocky) surfaces, the Lambert reflectance function is used (Lacerda and Jewitt, 2007). The conversion of visible illuminated area to magnitude is elaborated upon in section 5.2.2.

All of these parameters, taken together, form the “schematics” of a given model contact binary, describing its shape, size, mass, orbit, and brightness.

The process of creating a model lightcurve which can thus be roughly broken down into three steps: (1) modeling the physical parameters of the objects and their orbits, (2) calculating the visible illuminated area of the binary over the course of a full orbit, and (3) converting visible area to magnitude in order to create a model lightcurve. The first two steps are discussed below. Steps two and three are treated in Chapter 5.

4.1 Modeling Contact Binaries as Spheres

A model of small Solar System objects as contact or near-contact binaries was introduced by Wijesinghe and Tedesco (1979), who modeled the distinctive lightcurve of 171 Ophelia as a pair of spheres. This approach forgoes much of the accuracy derived from considering contact binaries as tidally deformed, but has the advantage of being the simplest possible model and being analytically tractable. As many of the projection geometry challenges inherent to modeling observations of contact binaries are far more complicated when discussed in the context of ellipsoids, we will introduce them first in the context of paired spheres.

Determining the total illuminated area of a contact binary consisting of paired spheres is a relatively straightforward process. As spherical objects always present the same sun-facing area regardless of their rotation, any changes in illuminated area will be the result of partial or total occultation of one of the component parts. Once the relative radii of the spheres and their projected separation is known, the area A of overlap can be calculated as follows:

$$A = r^2 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d^2 + r^2 - R^2}{2dr} \right) + R^2 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d^2 + R^2 - r^2}{2dr} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{(-d + r + R)(d + r - R)(d - r + R)(d + r + R)} \quad (8)$$

where R and r are the radii of the two spheres (and of their projected circles) and d is the separation between the centers of the two (Weisstein, 2015). The total illuminated area can then be calculated simply by adding the projected areas of the two circles and subtracting A .

Determining what fraction of the illuminated area is visible is a more complicated problem. As figure 22 shows, the projected area of the contact binary when viewed from the Sun differs from the projected area seen from the Earth as a function of the phase angle α . With an increase in α , the visible area will decrease as more of the area projected on Earth’s sky is the “night side” of the object. At high phase angles there may also be overlap between the two component

parts' projected areas when viewed from Earth that must be taken into account separately.

Fortunately, since KBOs are tens of AU from both the Sun and Earth, it is a good approximation for Earth-based observations to set the phase angle to zero. This will lead errors on the order of 1% in the accuracy of model lightcurves, an acceptable approximation. Models which rely on this approximation are unsuitable for generating accurate model lightcurves of less distant objects such as Main Belt asteroids and near-Earth objects, as they are commonly observed at large α .

Figure 22: Diagram of viewing geometry of a two-sphere close binary, from Wijesinghe and Tedesco (1979). At higher phase angles, as is depicted here, an Earth-based observer is looking partially at each component part's “night side” and there is visual overlap between the two objects despite neither being in the other’s shadow. Due to the extremely low phase angles at which KBOs are observed, it is a reasonable approximation to disregard this complicating element of contact binaries’ projection geometry.

4.2 Modeling Contact Binaries as Ellipsoids

Treating the objects as ellipsoids allows us to more precisely model object shapes while maintaining the analytical advantage of axial symmetry. This is an important improvement, given that two tidally locked rubble piles of similar size will undergo significant tidal deformation (Gnat and Sari, 2010). Accounting for this deformation is crucial in developing a more accurate model of a given binary system. However, the model has two additional free parameters (i.e. three

independent axes rather than one), greatly complicating the problem.

Fortunately, this problem can be simplified by modeling each component body as a Roche ellipsoid using the method set out by Chandrasekhar (1962). This process constructs a gravitational equipotential surface and treats each object as a fluid which fills that surface uniformly. In doing so we can solve for each body separately as a satellite of the other, and effectively model symmetric tidal deformation while disregarding the negligible effects of asymmetries in the each body's gravitational field (Leone et al, 1984). We can thus extract axial ratios b/a and c/a (where a is taken as the long axis, pointing toward the system's center of mass, b is the other axis located in the rotational plane, and c is the axis perpendicular to the rotational plane) for any given density ρ , mass ratio q , and angular velocity ω (derived from the observed period). ρ is taken to be identical for both component parts of the contact binary.

$$[(3+q)a^2 + c^2] \frac{\omega^2}{\pi G \rho (1+q)} = 2(A_1 a^2 - A_3^2), \quad (9)$$

$$[qb^2 + c^2] \frac{\omega^2}{\pi G \rho (1+q)} = 2(A_2 b^2 - A_3 c^2), \quad (10)$$

where

$$A_1 = abc \int_0^\infty (a^2 + u)^{-\frac{3}{2}} (b^2 + u)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (c^2 + u)^{-\frac{1}{2}} du, \quad (11)$$

$$A_2 = abc \int_0^\infty (a^2 + u)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (b^2 + u)^{-\frac{3}{2}} (c^2 + u)^{-\frac{1}{2}} du, \quad (12)$$

$$A_3 = abc \int_0^\infty (a^2 + u)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (b^2 + u)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (c^2 + u)^{-\frac{3}{2}} du. \quad (13)$$

We solved these equations numerically for c/a and q using a range of input values of b/a and ρ , with a set to 1 in each case (see 5.3). For each pair of input values of b/a and ρ , and resulting values of c/a and q , we then computed a complementary set of axial parameters for the companion body in each case (a' , b' , c') by setting the mass ratio equal to $(1/q)$. Solution sets were then discarded if they were physically implausible. This occurred when the two ellipsoids physically overlapped with each other, were too elongated to prevent rotational fission (see section 1.2.2), or if ρ was less than 500 or more than 10,000 (Lacerda and Jewitt, 2007).

4.3 Modeling Binary Orbits

The next step for each physically allowed binary pair was to calculate the orbital parameters of each. We did so by calculating the mass of each component using its modeled dimensions and densities and assuming circular Keplerian rotation (as would likely be the case for a binary in or near contact) to compute the separation of each object from the mutual center of mass in units relative to the long axis of the primary.

We then determined the two-dimensional position of each object as a function of orbital phase. Cases where the total separation l between the two objects was less than the sum $a + a'$ of the long axes of the two objects were then discarded.

Figure 23: Orbital positions for each of two near-contact binaries modeled using equations 9-13. The positions shown are for the center of each body. Ellipses are shown to visualize the approximate size ratio between the objects and to show that they are at opposite phase. Due to the high mass ratio (3.5) in the binary on the left, the orbit of the larger body is significantly smaller than that of the smaller body. However, in the binary on the right, the mass ratio is much lower (1.2), and the sizes of the two component bodies' orbits are very similar to one another.

5 Simulating Lightcurves

In order to compare models to data that we collect on 2001 QG₂₉₈ and other contact and near-contact binary KBOs, we must not only develop a library of physically allowable object sizes, dimensions, and orbits, but also calculate what we would see when taking lightcurves of those objects. This process is a complicated one, which requires us to proceed through several steps in order to produce a simulated lightcurve of a given model binary, as follows:

1. *Determining the illuminated area of each component of the binary independently:* As each half of a contact binary orbits the other, it rotates around the binary center of mass. Given that these objects are likely to be highly elongated due to tidal forces (as discussed in sections 2.1 and 4.2), the illuminated area of each will change significantly depending on whether its long or short axis is pointed toward the Sun.
2. *Determining the visible area of each component of the binary independently:* This process is similar to the determination of illuminated area discussed above. Over the course of each ellipsoidal component's rotation, the Earth-facing surface area will change depending on viewing geometry. For KBOs, this will be very nearly identical to the Sun-facing area due to their very low maximum phase angle. However, creating a model sufficiently versatile to account for the effect of phase angle allows our code to be repurposed for studies of NEAs and Main Belt asteroids as well as contact binaries in the Kuiper Belt. Both of these effects are discussed in section 5.2.1.2.
3. *Accounting for eclipses between the two components of the binary:* Depending on the inclination of the binary relative to the observer's line of sight, one half of it may either be casting a shadow on the other or obstructing the observer's view of it. This reduction in illuminated and/or visible surface area must be determined and subtracted from the total visible, illuminated area. This process is discussed in section 5.2.1.3.
4. *Accounting for reflectance properties:* Depending on its surface properties a KBO, or other small Solar System object, may reflect incoming light very differently. There are two main categories of surfaces in which we are interested. The first is high-albedo icy surfaces which randomly scatter incoming light, for which we use the Lambert reflectance function. The second is low-albedo rocky surfaces whose light scatter is dependent on the incident angle of light reflecting off the surface, for which we use the Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function. Surface reflectance is discussed in section 5.2.2.

5. *Integrating over the total visible, illuminated area of both components of the binary:* This final step incorporates the previous four: steps one, two, and three determine the limits of integration, while step four provides a multiplicative factor which must be applied to each dA of surface area while integrating. Performing this integration at each point over a full rotational period of a model binary should yield a highly accurate model lightcurve.

5.1 An Analytical Approach to Simulated Lightcurves

Our first attempt to generate model lightcurves began with an analytical approach to determining the illuminated area of the two modeled ellipsoids individually at each point in their orbit. This method proved prohibitively complex, but the mathematical and conceptual framework that it established was useful when developing our second, numerical approach.

The problem of calculating the illuminated area essentially reduces to determining the projected semimajor axes of the ellipsoid when viewed from the Sun. To begin, we assumed a zero-inclination system. In this case the projection of the semimajor axis perpendicular to the orbital plane (c) remains the same throughout the object's rotation, and the projected axis parallel to the orbital plane is a function of a and b (as defined in section 4.2). We were not successful in developing this method sufficiently to accommodate for contact binary whose rotation was inclined relative to its orbit.

First we calculated the horizontal semimajor axis of each object's projected ellipse (when viewed along the illumination vector). We initialized a two-dimensional array of X and Y coordinates corresponding to points around the outside of the projected ellipse at a given rotational angle β . \hat{X} was defined as perpendicular to the observer's line of sight (equal, in this case, to the incoming light from the Sun) and \hat{Y} as parallel to it, with $\beta = 0$ defined as the long axis of the ellipse lying perpendicular to the X -axis. The X and Y coordinates of points around the circumference of the ellipse were then calculated as a function of α and β :

$$x(\alpha, \beta) = a \cos(\alpha) \cos(\beta) - b \sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta) \quad (14)$$

and

$$y(\alpha, \beta) = a \cos(\alpha) \sin(\beta) + b \sin(\alpha) \cos(\beta) \quad (15)$$

In order to re-center the ellipse at the origin, the translations

$$x + a \cos(\alpha) \cos(\beta) - b \sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta) \quad (16)$$

and

$$y + a \cos(\alpha) \sin(\beta) + b \sin(\alpha) \cos(\beta) \quad (17)$$

were then applied. The projected semimajor axis x_{proj} could then be extracted from the extrema of the X column of the resulting array, and the sun-facing two-dimensional area of the ellipse determined with the equation

$$\text{area} = \pi x_{proj} c \tag{18}$$

We repeated this process for both components of the binary, in order to determine the sun-facing area of each.

We then determined whether any part of the sun-facing area of each component was eclipsed in order to calculate the actual illuminated surface area. We used the algorithm of Hughes and Chraibi (2011), who determine the intersection points of two ellipses by combining the equations for each and solving the resultant quartic equation using a numerical implementation of Ferrari's formula given in Nonweiler (1967). With the borders of the overlap region defined by the intersections of the two ellipses (of which there can be one, two, three, or four) and their edges, the area of that region can be calculated by filling it with ellipse sectors and polygons of known area. The sum of these sectors and polygons of known area is equal to the total projected overlap between the two bodies (Hughes and Chraibi, 2011).

We then subtracted the area of overlap at each point in the binary's orbit from the total sun-facing area calculated earlier and determine the actual illuminated area of the binary.

With this step completed, we then calculated the total visible area of the contact binary. Figure 24 shows the total summed area (in relative units, with the long axis A set to 1) of the same two model binaries whose orbital positions are plotted in figure 23.

Figure 24: Summed visible area as a function of rotational phase for the same two modeled ellipsoids shown in figure 23. These plots clearly show the same general trend in visible area over the course of a full rotation seen in 2001 QG₂₉₈ and other contact binaries (as shown in figure 15), and the fact that the binary with the greater total surface area (on the bottom) has deeper periods of occultation verifies that our calculations of overlap area are yielding realistic results. While this plot does not account for reflectance and is not an actual lightcurve, it is a necessary and important step toward generating accurate simulated lightcurves for our model contact binaries.

Figure 24 is not a simulated lightcurve, in that it is subject to two severe limitations:

1. A significant limitation of the analytical approach lies in the difficulty of making the step from visible area to flux. As discussed in section 5.2.2, not all points on the surface of an object reflect an equal amount of light from the Sun toward the observer. Points toward the limb of an object must be weighted differently than those toward the center of its face depending on the reflectance function being used to model its brightness. This calculation would require a more computationally-intensive surface integral when computing the object's actual brightness. This in turn would negate the advantage in speed and efficiency provided by the analytical model for the visible area.
2. Despite repeated attempts to generalize the formulae to arbitrary orientations of the two objects in 3-dimensional space, we were unable to develop a

means of analytically modeling the binary through a full rotation in any orientation other than rotating edge-on in the plane of the ecliptic ($\epsilon = i = 0^\circ$). 2001 QG₂₉₈ is believed to rotate at an obliquity of almost 90 degrees, and all theorized contact binary formation mechanisms (with the exception of born binaries) are likely to contribute to produce some fraction of objects with obliquities too high to be approximated as zero (see section 1.2.1). A model which failed to account for this significant and highly variable parameter was obviously not sufficient.

Finally, as previously stated, our intent was to develop code which was sufficiently general as to be applicable to contact binaries throughout the Solar System. This would require a model which was not reliant on the $\alpha = 0$ approximation we used in our analytical approach to modeling KBO contact binaries.

5.2 Numerically Simulating Lightcurves

When it became clear that there was no readily apparent means of analytically modeling the brightness of a contact binary over a full orbital phase, we turned to a numerical method instead. While previous studies such as Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) and Lacerda (2011) have generated individual sets of synthetic contact binary lightcurves in the past, ours is the first general-purpose model to do so. We simulated the Earth-facing surface of each ellipsoid as a collection of individual points. We then were able to determine whether a given point was illuminated and visible based on its position relative to observation and illumination vectors \vec{V}_o and \vec{V}_i , and to weight its brightness appropriately according to the Lambert and Lommel-Seeliger reflectance functions, as discussed in section 5.2.2. There are two significant benefits to this approach:

1. Accurately modeling the geometry of a contact binary system, capturing more detail than simply the dimensions, locations, and orientations of its constituent objects. Our analytical approach in section 5.1 was not able to account for parameters like phase angle, orbital inclination, obliquity, and aspect angle. Now, however, we were able to incorporate all of them into our modeling, deriving phase angle and orbital inclination using observational ephemeris and fitting for both obliquity and aspect angle. This method provided a much more nuanced and accurate picture of how much of the contact binary's surface area would be visible at any given time. This step is discussed in sections 5.2.1.1 and 5.2.1.2.
2. Ready incorporation of the reflectance effects of different surface types, as discussed in the end of section 5.1. As we are already modeling the binary as

a set of points distributed across an ellipsoidal surface, it became relatively straightforward to weight the brightness of the points that were illuminated based on their angles to the vectors \vec{V}_o and \vec{V}_i —a necessary step when incorporating the effects of the Lommel-Seeliger and Lambert reflectance functions for rocky and icy surfaces, respectively. This approach (discussed in section 5.2.2) allowed us to make the final step from a plot of visible surface area (figure 24) to a simulated lightcurve.

5.2.1 Determining the Limits of Integration

The first step in integrating over the visible surface area of the ellipsoids was to determine the limits of integration. In the analytical approach (5.1), this step would have been limited to integrating over the projected Earth-facing surface area of the object. However, specifically accounting for \vec{V}_o and \vec{V}_i allowed us to take the effect of the phase angle α into account, further generalizing our model. We also had to account for several possible values of the obliquity and aspect angles, ϵ and θ . The process of calculating these vectors, and with them the limits of integration, is discussed in sections 5.2.1.1 and 5.2.1.2..

Figure 25: A visualization of three possible viewing geometries of a modeled near-contact binary. All images show the same pair of ellipsoids, illuminated face-on. Points in blue are brighter, while points in red are fainter. The outlines of the ellipses are shown in black. On the left, $\vec{V}_o = \vec{V}_i$, and so the observer is looking face-on at two fully illuminated projected ellipses. In the middle, \vec{V}_o is offset slightly from \vec{V}_i , and so part of the observer-facing area of each ellipsoid is not illuminated. On the right, \vec{V}_o is rotated such that the two objects are visually overlapping, and a section of the illuminated, Earth-facing area of the back object is obscured by the front object.

5.2.1.1 Calculating Observation Geometry

The first step in constructing a physical model of the light curve an observed contact binary system was to locate the observation and illumination vectors \vec{V}_o and \vec{V}_i relative to the two modeled ellipsoids. Knowing the angles between these vectors and the spin vector \vec{V}_S of the binary is crucial to understanding how much of the contact binary will be visible at a given point in its rotation, and thus how bright it will appear.

The vectors \vec{V}_i and \vec{V}_o are most easily defined in the (X, Y, Z) coordinate space in which the Sun is located at the origin and the $X - Y$ plane is defined as the orbital plane of the object being modeled such that the object's orbital angular momentum vector, $\vec{V}_L \parallel [0, 0, 1]$. In order to identify \vec{V}_i and \vec{V}_o we must have four pieces of information defined by the date and time of the initial observation:

1. The heliocentric distance of the target, d_\odot (in AU)
2. The geocentric distance of the target, d_\oplus (in AU)
3. The phase angle of the observation(s), α (in degrees)
4. The ecliptic latitude of the target, ϕ (in degrees)

A quick-reference table for these and all other variable names used here is shown at the end of this section, in table 5.2.1.1.

Since the target object lies, by definition, in the $X - Y$ plane, we can define the X -axis as lying directly along the position vector of the target. This position vector is equivalent to \vec{V}_i , giving us the first of the two vectors with which we are concerned:

$$\vec{V}_i = [d_\odot, 0, 0] \quad (19)$$

Determining \vec{V}_o is slightly more complicated, and requires us to make use of the remaining three observational parameters. The Z component of \vec{V}_o is the easiest to constrain, as it will be a function of ϕ . Specifically, since the object's orbit is defined as the $X - Y$ plane, the ecliptic will now be inclined relative to the $X - Y$ plane at an angle of $-\phi$ degrees. The sine of $-\phi$ is then equal to the Z component of \vec{V}_o divided by the magnitude of Earth's position vector—which can be reasonably approximated as 1 AU for any point in the year. Thus:

$$V_{o,z} = \sin(-\phi) \quad (20)$$

Figure 26: A visualization of the observation and illumination vectors \vec{V}_o and \vec{V}_i discussed in this section. Axes are in relative units, with 1 equal to the object's largest semiaxis. The object is viewed along the blue vector, \vec{V}_o , and illuminated along the red vector, \vec{V}_i . The angle between the two vectors is the phase angle α . While a KBO could not have such a large phase angle when observed from Earth, accounting for this difference is a necessary component of accurately modeling the brightness of a generalizable ellipsoidal object over a full rotation.

To determine the X and Y components of \vec{V}_o , we begin by taking the dot product of \vec{V}_i and \vec{V}_o :

$$\vec{V}_i \cdot \vec{V}_o = [d_\odot, 0, 0] \cdot [V_{o,x}, V_{o,y}, \sin(-\phi)] = V_{o,x}d_\odot \quad (21)$$

By the definition of the dot product, we also know that $\vec{V}_i \cdot \vec{V}_o$ will be equal to the magnitudes of the two vectors multiplied together and by the cosine of the angle between them. Since the angle between them is the phase angle α and the magnitudes of the two angles are d_\odot and d_\oplus , we know that

$$\vec{V}_i \cdot \vec{V}_o = V_{o,x}d_\odot = d_\odot d_\oplus \cos(\alpha) \quad (22)$$

thus,

$$V_{o,x} = d_\oplus \cos(\alpha) \quad (23)$$

Finally, to determine $\vec{V}_{o,y}$ we can use the fact that $\|\vec{V}_o\| = d_\oplus$:

$$\|\vec{V}_o\| = \sqrt{d_\oplus^2 \cos^2(\alpha) + V_{o,y}^2 + \sin^2(-\phi)} = d_\oplus \quad (24)$$

Squaring both sides, we get

$$d_\oplus^2 \cos^2(\alpha) + V_{o,y}^2 + \sin^2(-\phi) = d_\oplus^2 \quad (25)$$

And can solve for $\vec{V}_{o,y}$ to get

$$\vec{V}_{o,y} = \sqrt{d_\oplus^2 - d_\oplus^2 \cos^2(\alpha) - \sin^2(-\phi)} \quad (26)$$

Giving us all components of the observation vector \vec{V}_o as shown:

$$\vec{V}_o = \left[d_\oplus \cos(\alpha), \sqrt{d_\oplus^2 - d_\oplus^2 \cos^2(\alpha) - \sin^2(-\phi)}, \sin(-\phi) \right] \quad (27)$$

We next had to account for the obliquity ϵ and aspect angle θ . Both angles (visualized in figure 12) are defined relative to the spin vector \vec{V}_S of the binary, which is parallel to the rotational axis of the pair around their shared center of mass. As discussed in Lacerda (2011), the obliquity ϵ is defined as the angle between the object's orbital angular momentum vector and its spin vector, such that

$$\vec{V}_L \cdot \vec{V}_S = \|\vec{V}_L\| \|\vec{V}_S\| \cos(\epsilon) \quad (28)$$

Thus, a contact binary with $\epsilon = 0$ will be spinning exactly in the orbital plane, and one with $\epsilon = 90$ will be spinning perpendicular to it.

The aspect angle θ is defined as the angle between the observation vector and spin vector, such that

$$\vec{V}_o \cdot \vec{V}_S = \|\vec{V}_o\| \|\vec{V}_S\| \cos(\theta) \quad (29)$$

An increasing aspect angle is the reason suggested by Lacerda (2011) for the change in the Δm of 2001 QG₂₉₈ between 2003 and 2010 (see section 2.2). There is no way to constrain either of these angles based solely on observational ephemeris. Like dimensions and mass ratio they must be determined by fitting observational data to large ranges of possible values.

To generate a library of spin vectors and corresponding values of ϵ and θ , we first initialized an array of possible obliquities from $\epsilon = 0$ to $\epsilon = 60$ with a step size of 15, and from $\epsilon = 75$ to $\epsilon = 90$ with a step size of 1. Each of these obliquities could be associated with numerous different spin vectors lying on a cone centered around \vec{V}_L . This range of possible spin vectors corresponds to different aspect angles. However, not all obliquities can correspond to all aspect angles.

To determine which spin vectors are allowable for each value of ϵ , we began by calculating the maximum possible value of $\vec{V}_{S,x}$ given that, since $\vec{V}_L = [0, 0, 1]$,

$$\vec{V}_L \cdot \vec{V}_S = \|\vec{V}_S\| \cos(\epsilon) = \vec{V}_{S,z} \quad (30)$$

We then assigned $\vec{V}_{S,z} = 1$ and calculated possible values of $\vec{V}_{S,x}$ and $\vec{V}_{S,y}$ relative to it. Rearranging equation 30, this gave us

$$\cos \epsilon = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\vec{V}_{S,x}^2 + \vec{V}_{S,y}^2 + 1}} \quad (31)$$

Next, we determined the maximum magnitude of $\vec{V}_{S,x}$ by setting $\vec{V}_{S,y} = 0$ and solving for $\vec{V}_{S,x}$:

$$\|\vec{V}_{S,x,max}\| = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\cos^2(\epsilon)} - 1} \quad (32)$$

We then iterated over values of $\vec{V}_{S,x}$ from $-\vec{V}_{S,x,max}$ to $+\vec{V}_{S,x,max}$, calculating the magnitude of the Y component of the spin vector $\vec{V}_{S,y}$ for each value of $\vec{V}_{S,x}$ using equation 31:

$$\|\vec{V}_{S,y}\| = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\cos^2(\epsilon)} - \vec{V}_{S,x}^2 - 1} \quad (33)$$

This gave us two spin vectors for each value of $\vec{V}_{S,x}$: $[\vec{V}_{S,x}, \|\vec{V}_{S,y}\|, 1]$ and $[\vec{V}_{S,x}, -\|\vec{V}_{S,y}\|, 1]$. Each possible spin vector could then be used to calculate its corresponding value of θ by taking the dot product of \vec{V}_S and \vec{V}_o :

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{\vec{V}_S \cdot \vec{V}_o}{\|\vec{V}_S\| \|\vec{V}_o\|} \quad (34)$$

At this point, the final remaining step was to calculate visible, illuminated area (see section 5.2.1.2). This process is significantly simplified in a coordinate space aligned with \vec{V}_S . We thus rotated \vec{V}_i , \vec{V}_o , and \vec{V}_S into that space by constructing a rotational matrix R_{3D} to rotate \vec{V}_S onto the vector $\hat{Z} = [0, 0, 1]$ and then applying that same matrix transformation to \vec{V}_i and \vec{V}_o .

To determine R_{3D} , we first define \vec{v} as

$$\vec{v} = \vec{V}_o \hat{Z} \quad (35)$$

Next, we define the skew-symmetric cross-product matrix $[v]$ of \vec{v} as

$$[v] = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -\vec{v}[2] & \vec{v}[1] \\ \vec{v}[2] & 0 & -\vec{v}[0] \\ -\vec{v}[1] & \vec{v}[0] & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad (36)$$

Where $\vec{v}[0]$, $\vec{v}[1]$, and $\vec{v}[2]$ are the three elements of \vec{v} . R_{3D} can then be calculated using the following formula:

$$R_{3D} = I + [v] + [v]^2 \frac{1 - (\vec{v}_o \cdot \hat{Z})}{\|\vec{v}\|^2} \quad (37)$$

Where I is the three-dimensional identity matrix

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

Applying the R_{3D} transformation to \vec{V}_i , and \vec{V}_o shifts the two vectors into a coordinate space whose Z -axis is aligned with \vec{V}_S and whose $X - Y$ plane is aligned with the rotational plane of the ellipsoids, significantly simplifying the calculations that must be done in section 5.2.1.2.

5.2.1.2 Identifying Illuminated and Observable Surface Area

In order to determine the visible, illuminated area of an object, it is necessary to determine two illumination boundaries. Each is defined by an ellipse over which the

Variable	Definition
\vec{V}_o	The vector from a given object to the observer (“observation vector”)
\vec{V}_i	The vector from a given object to the Sun (“illumination vector”)
\vec{V}_s	A binary’s axis of rotation (spin vector)
d_\odot	Heliocentric distance (in AU)
d_\oplus	Geocentric distance (in AU)
α	Angle between \vec{V}_o and \vec{V}_i , in degrees (phase angle)
ϕ	Ecliptic latitude, in degrees
ϵ	Angle between \vec{V}_i and \vec{V}_s (obliquity)
θ	Angle between \vec{V}_o and \vec{V}_s (aspect angle)

Table 2: Reference table of variables used in this section.

surface normal \vec{n} is perpendicular to an incoming vector: $\vec{n} \perp \vec{V}_i$. Similarly, $\vec{n} \perp \vec{V}_o$ distinguishes between the side of the object which is facing the observer and the side which is facing away. The section of the ellipsoid’s surface which lies between these two ellipses is then the area that is both illuminated and observable, which we must then integrate over. These boundaries, and the section of the surface in question, are shown in figure 27.

Identifying the equations for these two ellipses is a nontrivial problem. However, doing so can be made far easier by performing translations, rotations, and transformations to each ellipsoid individually in order to be able to treat it like a sphere located at the origin, so that each elliptical boundary is transformed into a circle.

For the ellipsoid centered at (x_0, y_0, z_0) , we begin by translating the object to the origin using the vector \vec{t} , defined as:

$$\vec{t} = \begin{bmatrix} -x_0 \\ -y_0 \\ -z_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (38)$$

Assuming that the ellipsoid is still rotated relative to the X - and Y -axes by an angle θ , we must then apply a rotation matrix R to align it with the axes, defined

Figure 27: A visualization of the same model ellipsoid shown in figure 26, now showing the boundaries between the illuminated and dark sides of the object (red) and the sides facing toward and away from the observer (blue). The area to be integrated over is the surface between the red and blue ellipses (specifically, the section with the two arrows emerging from it). Determining the exact boundaries of this area is the purpose of the calculations laid out in section 5.2.1.2.

as follows:

$$R = \begin{vmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Deforming this ellipsoid into a sphere requires another matrix S to scale the axes according to the ellipsoid's semimajor axes a , b , and c :

$$S = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{a} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{b} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{c} \end{vmatrix} \quad (40)$$

Finally, the resulting axes must be rotated again so that the Z -axis is parallel to \vec{V}_o . Since this brings us to a coordinate frame with $\hat{Z} \parallel \vec{V}_S$, we were then able to use the value of \vec{V}_o which we calculated in section 5.2.1.1.

There are three different cases that had to be accounted for at this point, depending on the initial orientation of the sphere:

1. $\hat{Z} \parallel \vec{V}_o$: No rotation is necessary.
2. $\hat{Z} \parallel -\vec{V}_o$: The sphere is rotated by 180 degrees.
3. In all other cases, the rotation matrix R_{3D} must be calculated which rotates the unit observation vector \vec{V}_o onto \hat{Z} . We calculated this rotation matrix using the same method described in section 5.2.1.1, applying it in this instance to the equation for the ellipse itself.

This step greatly simplified the calculation of the $\vec{n} \perp \vec{V}_o$ ellipse. Having performed these transformations, that ellipse became a circle in the $X - Y$ plane:

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 + y^2 &= 1, \\ z &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

We then applied the inverse of each of these transformations and translations to \vec{V}_o and to equation 41. This allowed us to recover the equation for the elliptical boundary between the observer-facing and non-observer-facing sides of the ellipsoid in its original coordinate space. We then repeated the process outlined above to \vec{V}_i to determine the boundary between the illuminated and non-illuminated halves of the ellipsoid. This entire series of transformations is shown in the tiled sequence in figure 28.

Figure 28: A visualization of the process of geometric transformations discussed in section 5.2.1, going clockwise from top left. (A) shows an arbitrarily placed and oriented ellipsoid with observation and illumination vectors in blue and red. In (B), the ellipsoid is translated to the origin. In (C), it is rotated so that its semiaxes are aligned with the coordinate axes. In (D) it is transformed into a sphere. In (E) it is rotated such that the observation vector is aligned with the Z-axis. This makes the boundary between the observer-facing and non-observer-facing sides into a circle in the $X - Y$ plane, as shown in (F). The inverse of each of these steps is applied in (G)-(J), which transforms the circle back into the original elliptical boundary that we are seeking. This process is then repeated for the illumination vector to find the boundary between the “night” and “day” sides.

It can be shown analytically that this process preserves all necessary information as follows:

We first begin with the equation for an arbitrary ellipsoid with semimajor axes a, b, c ,

$$f_e = \frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} - 1 \quad (42)$$

As discussed at the start of this section, we are interested in the locus of points on this ellipsoid where the surface normal \vec{n} is perpendicular to an incoming vector \vec{v} , defined as (α, β, γ) . As \vec{n} is equivalently expressed as the gradient of f_e , this can be represented mathematically as the set of solutions to the equation

$$\nabla f_e \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad (43)$$

Since the gradient of f_e is

$$\nabla f_e = \left(\frac{2x}{a^2}, \frac{2y}{b^2}, \frac{2z}{c^2} \right) \quad (44)$$

Our solutions are the points that lie on the surface defined by

$$\frac{2x\alpha}{a^2} + \frac{2y\beta}{b^2} + \frac{2z\gamma}{c^2} = 0 \quad (45)$$

We must now show that this set of solutions is identical to the solution set yielded when we transform the ellipsoid into a sphere. In order to do so, we move to the (X, Y, Z) coordinate space, with $X = \frac{x}{a}, Y = \frac{y}{b}, Z = \frac{z}{c}$, and begin with the general equation for a sphere:

$$f_s = X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 - 1 \quad (46)$$

Once again, we are interested in the locus of points where the surface normal

$$\vec{v} = \nabla f_s = (2X, 2Y, 2Z) \quad (47)$$

is perpendicular to the incoming vector \vec{v} . However, as we are now in the (X, Y, Z) coordinate space, the same transformation that was applied to the ellipsoid must be applied to \vec{v} . This transformed vector will be represented as \vec{V} , with components (A, B, Γ) , where $A = \frac{\alpha}{a}, B = \frac{\beta}{b}, \Gamma = \frac{\gamma}{c}$. The equation whose solutions we are interested in, then, is

$$\nabla f_s \cdot \vec{V} = 2XA + 2YB + 2Z\Gamma = 0 \quad (48)$$

However, if we transform this equation back to the (x, y, z) coordinate space, it becomes apparent that this is equal to the solution set found in equation 45:

$$0 = 2XA + 2YB + 2Z\Gamma = 2 \cdot \frac{x}{a} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{a} + 2 \cdot \frac{y}{b} \cdot \frac{\beta}{b} + 2 \cdot \frac{z}{c} \cdot \frac{\gamma}{c} = 0 \quad (49)$$

This demonstrates that solutions found after transforming an ellipsoid to a sphere remain valid once the surface is transformed back to an ellipsoid.

5.2.1.3 Accounting for Visual Overlap

The final step in determining the limits of integration is accounting for visual overlap between the two objects. As discussed at the start of section 5.2, depending on the orientation of the two objects relative to one another, to the Earth, and to the Sun, one object might lie in front of the other along either the illumination or observation vector, with part of the back object being occluded by part of the front object. When overlap occurs along the illumination vector, some area of the back object will be in shadow, despite facing the Sun. When overlap occurs along the observation vector, some area of the back object will be obscured, despite facing the Earth (regardless of whether it is illuminated). Both of these cases must be modeled and our calculation of total area adjusted accordingly.

Since all points on the surface of each modeled ellipsoid are known throughout their mutual orbit, we also know at any given time which ellipsoid lies closer to the Earth or to the Sun. We could then calculate the projected extrema of each ellipsoid when viewed along each vector in order to determine whether or not there was any overlap. Making this initial binary determination eliminated the need for wasteful calculation in cases where there was no overlap. In cases where there was overlap, we then tested each point on the back object individually to see whether it lay within the convex hull⁴ of the front object. Points that lay within the front object's hull were then subtracted off the total surface area that was to be integrated over.

5.2.2 Reflectance

It is not sufficient simply to identify what area of each ellipsoid's surface we will be integrating over. We must also model the reflectance properties of the object's surface, as a degeneracy exists between surface composition and size—an object whose surface is more highly reflective may appear similar to a larger object whose surface is less reflective. The only KBOs whose reflectance properties are reasonably well known are those of the Pluto-Charon system, which was found by the New

⁴A convex hull is the smallest possible surface containing a given set of points. For our model ellipsoids, it can be visualized as an elastic sheet stretched over a set of individual points.

Horizons mission team to display enormously variable albedos and surface properties (Stern et al, 2015). However, the surface characteristics of the population of KBOs are unknown.

As such, we follow the model of Lacerda and Jewitt (2007). In their investigation of the rotational lightcurves of Solar System objects, Lacerda and Jewitt applied both the Lambert and Lommel-Seeliger reflectance functions to 2001 QG₂₉₈ in order to account for both icy and rocky surface compositions, respectively. These reflectance functions are introduced when performing the final integration over each model contact binary’s visible area, and are used to weight the brightness of each point on the ellipsoids’ surfaces. Summing these then gives the reflected flux toward the observer. Taking the logarithm of the resulting flux and multiplying by -2.5 yields the magnitude of the model binary at each phase in its rotation, which can be compared with the repeated observations..

5.2.2.1 The Lambert Reflectance Function

The Lambert reflectance function traces its origins to the *Photometria* of the Swiss mathematician and physicist Johann Heinrich Lambert, published in 1760. In it he characterized the function now known as Lambert’s Cosine Law, which describes the reflective properties of ideal diffusely reflecting surfaces (Lambert, 1760).

The key characteristic which Lambert identified was that light rays entering an ideal diffusely reflective surface will be multiply scattered and then leave the surface in a random direction (Lacerda and Jewitt, 2007). In effect, this means that a given point on such a surface will emit light isotropically, with its brightness depending solely on the angle i' between the surface normal \vec{n} at that point and the incoming light (along \vec{V}_i). Specifically, the relationship between a point’s radiant intensity r_L and i' is expressed as:

$$r_L \propto \mu_0 \tag{50}$$

Where $\mu_0 = \cos i'$ (hence the “Cosine Law”).

It is particularly significant that this equation includes no provision for e' , the angle of emission (the angle between the surface normal and \vec{V}_O). Since each point on a Lambertian surface emits isotropically, the surface as a whole will appear to be the same brightness regardless of where it is being observed from. A spherical or ellipsoidal Lambertian body will appear brightest at the intersection of \vec{V}_i and its surface, and fainter at greater distances (which translate to greater values of i).

The most typical example of a Lambertian surface, and one which would be commonly found among trans-Neptunian objects’ surfaces, is ice. Ice is a highly diffuse reflector, as it is composed of numerous small, transparent crystals. As

such, when simulating an icy surface, we use the Lambert function to weight the brightness of each point during integration. A Lambertian surface is shown at several angles of rotation in the left column of figure 29.

5.2.2.2 The Lommel-Seeliger Reflectance Function

The Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function is itself a somewhat simplified form of the Hapke model developed to model directional reflectances of Lunar-style regoliths (Hapke 1981, Wells and Hapke 1981). However, the Hapke function is very parameter-intensive, describing parameters such as single scattering albedo, macroscopic roughness angle, width and amplitude of the opposition surge, and asymmetry factor (Helfenstein et al 1996). These parameters cannot be solved for without a large number of observations sampling many different values of i' , e' , and α , which cannot be realistically obtained for terrestrial observations of KBOs.

Since it takes far fewer parameters into account, the Lommel-Seeliger function lacks much of this complexity and is far faster and easier to implement than the full Hapke model (Fairbairn 2005). This naturally sacrifices some of the precision of the Hapke function. However, Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) note that many of the Hapke parameters are less important when modeling the reflectance of KBOs.

The Lommel-Seeliger function works by modeling light penetrating a surface and encountering units of volume which attenuate it exponentially and scatter it isotropically. Despite modeling a relatively complex process, it is mathematically quite simple, as for each point it depends only on i' and e' :

$$r_{LS} = \frac{\mu_0}{\mu + \mu_0} \quad (51)$$

Where μ_0 is once again equal to $\cos i'$, and $\mu = \cos e'$.

In contrast to the Lambert reflectance function, a Lommel-Seeliger surface will appear different depending on its orientation relative to the observer (due to the dependence on e'). Points close to the intersection of \vec{V}_o will actually appear less bright, while points at a greater emission angle will get steadily brighter—translating to a “limb brightening” effect, as one sees when looking at the crescent Moon. Not surprisingly, the Lommel-Seeliger function is a suitable model for the “dusty” regoliths which arise on many airless worlds, such as the Moon and numerous asteroids (Hapke 2001). Thus, when simulating a rocky or regolith surface, we use the Lommel-Seeliger function to weight the brightness of each point during integration. A Lommel-Seeliger surface is shown at several angles of rotation in the central column of figure 29.

Figure 29: A comparison of simulated observations of a sphere at phase angles $\alpha = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ, 105^\circ,$ and 120° (Fairbairn, 2004). A Lambertian surface is shown on the left, a Lommel-Seeliger surface in the middle, and a uniform outline of the surface on the right for comparison. Note that the Lambertian surface shows limb darkening at $\alpha = 0$, while the Lommel-Seeliger surface is dimmer near the terminator and brighter along the limb at higher phase angles.

5.3 Library Generation

The last step before we began simulating contact binary lightcurves was to generate a large library of contact binaries with varying physical parameters and system geometries.

In creating a wide range of models, we focused primarily on achieving good coverage of a large range of mass ratio q as all other physical parameters (dimensions and density) are at least partly dependent on mass ratio. We tested values of q from 0.25 to 1.0, and axis ratios from 0.43 to 1.0. Outside of that range, most models are not physically allowable for the reasons discussed in section 4.2.

It was equally important to simulate lightcurves at a wide range of geometries (ϵ and θ). Since Lacerda (2011) predicted an obliquity of $90^\circ \pm 30$ for 2001 QG₂₉₈, we simulated obliquities from 0 to 75 with a step size of 15, and obliquities from 75 to 90 with a step size of 1. In order to test the range of θ predicted by Lacerda (2011), we simulated aspect angles from 60 to 90 with a step size of 2.

In total, this yielded 130 different contact binary models, each of which we tested at 300 different geometries for a total of 39,000 simulated lightcurves each for icy and rocky surface types. The total ranges and step sizes of physical and geometric parameters which we tested are shown in table 5.3.

Parameter	Minimum	Maximum	Interval
Physical Parameters			
q	0.25	1.00	0.01875
B/A	0.43	0.99	0.056
C/A	0.43	0.99	0.056
b/a	0.43	0.99	0.056
c/a	0.43	0.99	0.056
ρ	500	10000	-
Geometric Parameters			
ϵ	0°	75°	15°
ϵ	75°	90°	1°
θ	60°	90°	2°

Table 3: Range of physical and geometric parameters used in generating our library of contact binary models. No step size is shown for ρ as it was determined for each model using the dimensions, mass ratio, and period and assuming Keplerian rotation.

6 Analysis of Model Lightcurves

6.1 Creating a Lightcurve

Once we had generated the library of physical and geometric parameters laid out in section 5.3, modeled them at varying viewing geometry, and simulated lightcurves of each of them with both rocky and icy surfaces, we could finally fit our models to the available set of data. Doing so allows us to compare our results to those of Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) and Lacerda (2011) in order to verify that our best-fit model resembles each of theirs. This serves as a powerful verification tool for the accuracy of our methodology.

To construct a lightcurve, we select specific values for the physical parameters listed in Table 3, an example set being $q = 0.769$, $B/A = 0.933$, $C/A = 0.866$, $b/a = 0.907$, $c/a = 0.841$, $\rho = 1262$. These parameters give rise to a pair of objects resembling those shown in figure 30.

Figure 30: The model contact binary described by the parameters listed above. This is the same model binary shown in figure 9.

We then select a specific viewing geometry and orbital orientation of the object as described in section 5.2.1.1, and consider a full rotation of the binary pair. The binary in figure 30 is shown at a geometry of $\epsilon = 90$, $\theta = 90$, and its rotation will look like the visualization in figure 13.

At each phase of the orbital rotation we then integrate the total visible and illuminated area (as described in section 5.2.1) scaled by the appropriate reflectance function (as described in 5.2.2) and record the total observed flux as a function of orbital phase, giving rise to a lightcurve which looks like the one shown in figure 31. This process is repeated for all of the parameter sets and geometries generated in section 5.3.

6.2 Accounting for Phase Offset and χ^2 Fitting

The only complicating factor in fitting individual lightcurves to data is the potential for an offset between the zero-point of the model's phase compared to the data's phase. Throughout our study, $\phi = 0$ for the data lay midway between a minimum and maximum. This was established at that point purely because that was the rotational phase of the earliest point in the Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) data set (see figure 8). However, our model lightcurves were generated with $\phi = 0$ located at one of the minima, as that was a conceptually and computationally simple starting point.

We fitted over a series of phase offsets from 0 to 1 with a step size of 0.03, performing a brute-force χ^2 test to determine which offset best matched each lightcurve to the data. For each offset, we used numpy's⁵ interpolation function to create a set of model data points at corresponding phases to the observational data points. We then normalized both the observational data and the model lightcurve such that both were at a magnitude of 0 at a rotational phase of 0.6, roughly corresponding to the second maximum and calculated the sum of the squared difference between the model and observational magnitude at each point. The phase offset with the minimum χ^2 value was then applied to the model data's phase, as shown in figure 31. This process was done twice for each simulated lightcurve: once to determine its goodness-of-fit to the 2003 data, and once to determine its goodness-of-fit to the 2010 data. We then recorded the minimum χ^2 value for each lightcurve at its best-fit offset.

Given the impact suggested by Lacerda (2011) of 2001 QG₂₉₈'s diminishing aspect angle on its lightcurve (see section 2.2), it was important to confirm that decreasing θ for a given physical model resulted in a decrease in Δm . This also served as a qualitative check on the accuracy of our model. Figure 32 shows a comparison between several of our own synthetic lightcurves at varying θ , verifying this trend.

⁵<http://www.numpy.org/>

Figure 31: A plot of the 2010 observations of 2001 QG₂₉₈ from Lacerda (2011) and a model lightcurve. A χ^2 fit must be performed for each lightcurve in order to determine the phase shift to apply to it in order to line it up with the observational data. Here, the original model data is shown in green, and the offset model in red. Note that, while this particular model is not a good fit to the observational data, the script is still able to shift it accurately so that the dips in the model lightcurve line up with those in the observational data.

Figure 32: Simulated lightcurves of a model contact binary observed at a constant obliquity of 90 degrees and aspect angles of 64, 70, 76, 82, and 88 degrees. Note that Δ mag decreases steadily with aspect angle, and that the lightcurve that appears to most closely match 2010 the observational data (shown in blue) is at an aspect angle of 74 degrees, matching the findings presented by Lacerda (2011).

6.3 Determination of Error

3σ confidence intervals for our best-fit model assuming an icy surface are shown in table 6.4. We calculated error for each physical and geometric parameter by taking the difference between the parameters of our best-fit model and those of the model with the highest χ^2 model within 3σ . The Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) data contained 113 data points, and the Lacerda (2011) data contained 61 data points. Given that we were fitting 8 different free parameters, this gave 105 degrees of freedom ($3\sigma = 150$) when fitting the Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) data and 53 degrees of freedom ($3\sigma = 86$) when fitting the Lacerda (2011) data.

6.4 χ^2 Fitting Results

Comparing our best-fit physical parameters and geometry of 2001 QG₂₉₈ to the results of previous works served as a means of verifying the accuracy of our model. In the case of the 2003 fits, we were able to compare our best-fit parameters to those found in Lacerda and Jewitt (2007). No analogous fit has been performed for binary dimensions, mass ratio, or density to the 2010 data. We were able to check the best-fit geometry yielded by our model to the predictions regarding ϵ and θ made by Lacerda (2011) (see section 2.2).

For each data set, we performed two fits: one for each surface reflectance function. Given that Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) suggested that 2001 QG₂₉₈ might have a surface with intermediate properties between those of an icy Lambertian surface and a regolith Lommel-Seeliger surface, it was important to have fits using both functions.

In the case of a Lambertian surface, our best-fit physical and geometric parameters closely matched the results of Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) in all cases. Our fit gave $\epsilon > 80^\circ$ when fitting both the 2003 and 2010 data, in good agreement with the $\epsilon = 90_{-30}$ prediction from Lacerda (2011). The 16° decrease in the fitted value for θ is an exact match for the Lacerda (2011) prediction that the motion of 2001 QG₂₉₈ in its orbit from 2003 to 2010 should lead to a change of 16° in its aspect angle. This strongly suggests that our model is doing an accurate job fitting both sets of data and extracting plausible, accurate values for the object's system geometry. The best-fit parameters are shown in table 6.4, and plots of the best-fit solutions to the 2003 and 2010 data are shown in figure 33. The presence of structure in the residuals of the 2003 fit is likely due to 2001 QG₂₉₈ having been most accurately modeled as an intermediate surface between the Lambert and Lommel-Seeliger functions, as suggested by Lacerda and Jewitt (2007).

Unfortunately, more work seems to be required in fitting rocky surfaces. Our model struggled to fit both the 2003 and 2010 data using the Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function, producing an implausible best-fit lightcurve and not accurately matching the results of either Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) or Lacerda (2011). This lack of accuracy is reflected in the plots in figure 33. We are continuing to refine our implementation of the Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function, and hope to have more accurate and useful results for use in future studies. Both the successes and flaws revealed in this round of fitting clearly reflect the value of performing thorough, detailed testing, and comparing our results to those of previous studies.

	ϵ ($^\circ$)	θ ($^\circ$)	q	B/A	C/A	b/a	c/a	ρ
LJ 2007	90	90	0.44	0.85	0.77	0.53	0.49	659
2003 Fit	89 ± 11	86 ± 1	0.33 ± 0	0.69 ± 0.12	0.58 ± 0.16	0.68 ± 0.20	0.61 ± 0.18	573 ± 137
2010 Fit	82 ± 3	70 ± 16	0.33 ± 0	0.81 ± 0.13	0.74 ± 0.07	0.48 ± 0.18	0.43 ± 0.17	710 ± 62

Table 4: A comparison of best-fit parameters determined by Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) to the 2003 lightcurve of 2001 QG₂₉₈ and those extracted using our model from the 2003 and 2010 (Lacerda 2011) data. Errors shown are for a 3σ confidence interval. When modeling an icy (Lambertian) surface, all parameters predicted using our model are in close agreement with those predicted by Lacerda and Jewitt (2007), and the change in θ between 2003 and 2010 matches what would be expected from 2001 QG₂₉₈'s progress in its orbit. Because of flaws in our implementation of the Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function, we currently have no useful best-fit parameters for a rocky surface..

Figure 33: Lightcurves 2001 QG₂₉₈ plotted in blue, with best-fit model lightcurves synthesized by our model overplotted in green. The top row shows data taken in 2003 by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004), and the bottom row shows data taken in 2010 by Lacerda (2011). The left column shows fits predicting an icy (Lambertian) surface, while the right column shows fits predicting a rocky (Lommel-Seeliger) surface.

7 Conclusion

7.1 Future Directions

Previous studies of Solar System contact binaries have used a wide variety of methods for fitting and interpretation of lightcurves, all of them requiring labor-intensive “ground-up” development. As such, the most significant result of our research is that, once our implementation of the Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function is fully functional, we will make our code available to other researchers.

There are numerous ways in which the code developed for this study could be leveraged in projects focusing on contact binaries throughout our Solar System.

The most immediate next step would be to take additional data on 2001 QG₂₉₈ and fit it to see if the trend observed by Lacerda (2010) has continued in the intervening years. If 2001 QG₂₉₈ is indeed at an obliquity near 90° and its aspect angle has continued to decrease, we would expect to see a $\Delta m < 0.5$ and continuing to decrease. If future observations match that prediction, we would be able to more definitively determine that object’s system geometry. Doing so would also provide additional opportunities to refine the accuracy of our physical modeling method by ensuring that the coherence seen between our best-fit 2003 and 2010 parameters is matched by fits to future observations at an even lower aspect angle. Depending on the orientation of 2001 QG₂₉₈, the magnitude of its aspect angle could be anywhere between 90° and $90 - 2.29n$ degrees, where n is equal to the number of years since initial observations in 2003 (see section 2.2). Lightcurves of 2001 QG₂₉₈ providing a higher degree of both *rotational* phase coverage and *orbital* phase coverage could significantly reduce this ambiguity.

The applicability of our model and code is not restricted to studies of KBOs. Our implementation is capable of modeling objects at arbitrarily high phase angles, making it equally suitable for future research on contact binaries in the Main Belt and elsewhere in the inner Solar System (including the Near-Earth Object population). Given the large Kuiper Belt contact binary fraction predicted by Sheppard and Jewitt (2003) and Lacerda (2011) and discussed in section 2.2, the greatest utility of our code will still lie in recognizing and classifying additional contact binaries beyond Neptune. Given that 2001 QG₂₉₈ remains the only known trans-Neptunian contact binary, many more contact binaries will need to be discovered in that region in order to test the predicted contact binary fraction (Sheppard and Jewitt, 2003; Lacerda, 2010).

While there are numerous methods which could be attempted in order to identify more of these objects, we propose three specific studies that could be undertaken:

1. A focused study of the candidate contact binary KBOs identified by Shep-

pard and Jewitt (2003). In addition to categorizing 2001 QG₂₉₈ as a contact binary, that work identified four other objects as having a “medium” or “high” chance of being contact binaries in nature: 2000 GN₁₇₁, (33128) 1998 BU₄₈, (26308) 1998 SM₁₆₅, and (32929) 1995 QT₉. Follow-up observations of these objects could show evolution in Δm consistent (or inconsistent) with being contact binaries. Fits of future data and of the data taken by Sheppard and Jewitt (2003) using our code could thus help to conclusively determine the status of these four objects.

2. A more generalized study searching for candidate contact binary objects in all-sky survey data. Pan-STARRS provides an immediately abundant and likely source for such data. The Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) comes online in 2020. When it does so, a large number of additional KBOs will be found and have suitable lightcurves for fitting with our model (Ivezic et al, 2008). Contact binaries identified in this sample could subsequently be observed as their aspect angle increases or decreases to see if their Δm evolves in the same way that 2001 QG₂₉₈'s has.
3. A large-scale synthetic survey of contact binaries in the Kuiper Belt. Our code is a widely applicable and highly adaptable tool for generating model contact binaries and their lightcurves. It could be used to simulate the results of large surveys of KBOs under varying conditions. Parameters such as the contact binary fraction in the Kuiper Belt and the distribution of contact binary spin vectors and dimensions could be varied, and the effects of those changes observed in survey results. Such a study could then be compared to existing and future data sets of KBO observations in order to help determine the total number of contact binaries in the Kuiper Belt and whether they have a preferential orientation or size.

7.2 Summary

We present a new and highly versatile method for fitting the lightcurves of Solar System contact binaries. Our process has generated a large library of synthetic contact binaries with varying viewing geometries, mass ratios, dimensions, and densities. For each model binary the code determines the total visible illuminated area of each over a full rotational phase, weights the brightness of points on the surface according to either the Lambert or Lommel-Seeliger reflectance function (for icy and regolith surfaces, respectively), and then integrates the flux over that area. This yields a set of model lightcurves which can be compared to observational data for a given object using a simple χ^2 fit.

We have tested this model by performing fits on lightcurves taken in 2003 and

2010 by Sheppard and Jewitt (2004) and Lacerda (2011), respectively, comparing our best-fit model to those found by Lacerda and Jewitt (2007) and Lacerda (2011). Our best-fit Lambertian model closely matched those of previous studies, suggesting that it is highly accurate; however, our Lommel-Seeliger model did not yield plausible results, and as such will require further fine-tuning.

Once the problems with modeling regolith surfaces are resolved, our model and the associated code will represent a widely applicable set of tools both for modeling individual contact binaries and for enabling broader studies of contact binary abundance and characteristics throughout the Kuiper Belt.

References

- [Asphaug and Benz(1996)] Asphaug, E., Benz, W. 1996. Size, Density, and Structure of Comet Shoemaker-Levy 9 Inferred from the Physics of Tidal Breakup. *Icarus* 121, 225-248.
- [Batygin and Brown(2016)] Batygin, K., Brown, M. E. 2016. Evidence for a Distant Giant Planet in the Solar System. *The Astronomical Journal* 151, 22.
- [Bottke et al.(2002)] Bottke, W. F., Jr., Cellino, A., Paolicchi, P., Binzel, R. P. 2002. Asteroids III. Asteroids III, W. F. Bottke Jr., A. Cellino, P. Paolicchi, and R. P. Binzel (eds), University of Arizona Press, Tucson, 2002. ISBN: 978-0-8165-2281-1 .
- [Bottke et al.(2005)] Bottke, W. F., Durda, D. D., Nesvorný, D., Jedicke, R., Morbidelli, A., Vokrouhlický, D., Levison, H. F. 2005. Linking the collisional history of the main asteroid belt to its dynamical excitation and depletion. *Icarus* 179, 63-94.
- [Bottke and Melosh(1996)] Bottke, W. F., Melosh, H. J. 1996. Formation of asteroid satellites and doublet craters by planetary tidal forces. *Nature* 381, 51-53.
- [Bottke et al.(2006)] Bottke, W. F., Nesvorný, D., Grimm, R. E., Morbidelli, A., O'Brien, D. P. 2006. Iron meteorites as remnants of planetesimals formed in the terrestrial planet region. *Nature* 439, 821-824.
- [Bottke et al.(2006)] Bottke, W. F., Jr., Vokrouhlický, D., Rubincam, D. P., Nesvorný, D. 2006. The Yarkovsky and Yorp Effects: Implications for Asteroid Dynamics. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences* 34, 157-191.
- [Brasser and Morbidelli(2013)] Brasser, R., Morbidelli, A. 2013. Oort cloud and Scattered Disc formation during a late dynamical instability in the Solar System. *Icarus* 225, 40-49.
- [Burns et al.(1979)] Burns, J. A., Lamy, P. L., Soter, S. 1979. Radiation forces on small particles in the solar system. *Icarus* 40, 1-48.
- [Canup and Asphaug(2001)] Canup, R. M., Asphaug, E. 2001. Origin of the Moon in a giant impact near the end of the Earth's formation. *Nature* 412, 708-712.
- [Carter et al.(2011)] Carter, J. A., Winn, J. N., Holman, M. J., Fabrycky, D., Berta, Z. K., Burke, C. J., Nutzman, P. 2011. The Transit Light Curve

Project. XIII. Sixteen Transits of the Super-Earth GJ 1214b. *The Astrophysical Journal* 730, 82.

- [Cellino et al.(1985)] Cellino, A., Pannunzio, R., Zappala, V., Farinella, P., Paolich, P. 1985. Do we observe light curves of binary asteroids?. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 144, 355-362.
- [Chambers(2011)] Chambers, K. C. 2011. The First year of the Pan-STARRS 1 System: Surveys, Cadences, Data Products, and Performance. *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society* 43, 113.01.
- [Chandrasekhar(1987)] Chandrasekhar, S. 1987. *Ellipsoidal figures of equilibrium*. New York : Dover, 1987. .
- [Chandrasekhar(1969)] Chandrasekhar, S. 1969. *Ellipsoidal figures of equilibrium*. The Silliman Foundation Lectures, New Haven: Yale University Press, 1969 .
- [Chandrasekhar and Lebovitz(1962)] Chandrasekhar, S., Lebovitz, N. R. 1962. The Potentials and the Superpotentials of Homogeneous Ellipsoids.. *The Astrophysical Journal* 136, 1037.
- [Cook and Franklin(1970)] Cook, A. F., Franklin, F. A. 1970. An explanation of the light curve of Iapetus. *Icarus* 13, 282-291.
- [Correia et al.(2003)] Correia, A. C. M., Laskar, J., de Surgy, O. N. 2003. Long-term evolution of the spin of Venus. I. theory. *Icarus* 163, 1-23.
- [Dalle Ore et al.(2009)] Dalle Ore, C. M., and 12 colleagues 2009. Composition of KBO (50000) Quaoar. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 501, 349-357.
- [Davies et al.(2008)] Davies, J. K., McFarland, J., Bailey, M. E., Marsden, B. G., Ip, W.-H. 2008. The Early Development of Ideas Concerning the Transneptunian Region. *The Solar System Beyond Neptune* 11-23.
- [Davis and Farinella(1997)] Davis, D. R., Farinella, P. 1997. Collisional Evolution of Edgeworth-Kuiper Belt Objects. *Icarus* 125, 50-60.
- [DeMeo et al.(2009)] DeMeo, F. E., Binzel, R. P., Slivan, S. M., Bus, S. J. 2009. An extension of the Bus asteroid taxonomy into the near-infrared. *Icarus* 202, 160-180.
- [Descamps and Marchis(2008)] Descamps, P., Marchis, F. 2008. Angular momentum of binary asteroids: Implications for their possible origin. *Icarus* 193, 74-84.

- [Descamps et al.(2011)] Descamps, P., and 18 colleagues 2011. Triplicity and physical characteristics of Asteroid (216) Kleopatra. *Icarus* 211, 1022-1033.
- [Descamps(2015)] Descamps, P. 2015. Dumb-bell-shaped equilibrium figures for fiducial contact-binary asteroids and EKBOs. *Icarus* 245, 64-79.
- [Desch(2007)] Desch, S. J. 2007. Mass Distribution and Planet Formation in the Solar Nebula. *The Astrophysical Journal* 671, 878-893.
- [Duncan et al.(1988)] Duncan, M., Quinn, T., Tremaine, S. 1988. The origin of short-period comets. *The Astrophysical Journal* 328, L69-L73.
- [Dunlap and Gehrels(1969)] Dunlap, J. L., Gehrels, T. 1969. Minor Planets. III. Lightcurves of a Trojan Asteroid. *The Astronomical Journal* 74, 796.
- [Durda(1996)] Durda, D. D. 1996. The Formation of Asteroidal Satellites in Catastrophic Collisions. *Icarus* 120, 212-219.
- [Edgeworth(1949)] Edgeworth, K. E. 1949. The origin and evolution of the Solar System. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 109, 600-609.
- [Edgeworth(1961)] Edgeworth, K. E. 1961. *The earth, the planets, and the stars.* New York, Macmillan, 1961. .
- [Elliot et al.(2005)] Elliot, J. L., and 10 colleagues 2005. The Deep Ecliptic Survey: A Search for Kuiper Belt Objects and Centaurs. II. Dynamical Classification, the Kuiper Belt Plane, and the Core Population. *The Astronomical Journal* 129, 1117-1162.
- [Fairbairn(2005)] Fairbairn, M. B. 2005. Planetary Photometry: The Lommel-Seeliger Law. *Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society of Canada* 99, 92.
- [Farinella and Davis(1992)] Farinella, P., Davis, D. R. 1992. Collision rates and impact velocities in the Main Asteroid Belt. *Icarus* 97, 111-123.
- [Fernandez(1980)] Fernandez, J. A. 1980. On the existence of a comet belt beyond Neptune. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 192, 481-491.
- [Fernandez and Ip(1984)] Fernandez, J. A., Ip, W.-H. 1984. Some dynamical aspects of the accretion of Uranus and Neptune - The exchange of orbital angular momentum with planetesimals. *Icarus* 58, 109-120.
- [Fitzsimmons (2011)] Fitzsimmons, A. 2011 Asteroid Colours in the PS1 Photometric System. Unpublished Pan-STARRS Internal Collaboration Document.

- [Gladman(2005)] Gladman, B. 2005. The Kuiper Belt and the Solar System's Comet Disk. *Science* 307, 71-75.
- [Gladman et al.(2001)] Gladman, B., Kavelaars, J. J., Petit, J.-M., Morbidelli, A., Holman, M. J., Loredo, T. 2001. The Structure of the Kuiper Belt: Size Distribution and Radial Extent. *The Astronomical Journal* 122, 1051-1066.
- [Gnat and Sari(2010)] Gnat, O., Sari, R. 2010. Equilibrium Configurations of Synchronous Binaries: Numerical Solutions and Application to Kuiper Belt Binary 2001 QG₂₉₈. *The Astrophysical Journal* 719, 1602-1618.
- [Goldreich et al.(2002)] Goldreich, P., Lithwick, Y., Sari, R. 2002. Formation of Kuiper-belt binaries by dynamical friction and three-body encounters. *Nature* 420, 643-646.
- [Gomes et al.(2005)] Gomes, R., Levison, H. F., Tsiganis, K., Morbidelli, A. 2005. Origin of the cataclysmic Late Heavy Bombardment period of the terrestrial planets. *Nature* 435, 466-469.
- [Gradie and Tedesco(1982)] Gradie, J., Tedesco, E. 1982. Compositional structure of the asteroid belt. *Science* 216, 1405-1407.
- [Hapke(1981)] Hapke, B. 1981. Bidirectional reflectance spectroscopy. I - Theory. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 86, 3039-3054.
- [Hapke and Wells(1981)] Hapke, B., Wells, E. 1981. Bidirectional reflectance spectroscopy. II - Experiments and observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 86, 3055-3060.
- [Hapke(2001)] Hapke, B. 2001. Space weathering from Mercury to the asteroid belt. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 106, 10039-10074.
- [Harmon et al.(2010)] Harmon, J. K., Nolan, M. C., Giorgini, J. D., Howell, E. S. 2010. Radar observations of 8P/Tuttle: A contact-binary comet. *Icarus* 207, 499-502.
- [Hartmann and Cruikshank(1978)] Hartmann, W. K., Cruikshank, D. P. 1978. The nature of Trojan asteroid 624 Hektor. *Icarus* 36, 353-366.
- [Helfenstein et al.(1996)] Helfenstein, P., and 10 colleagues 1996. Galileo Photometry of Asteroid 243 Ida. *Icarus* 120, 48-65.
- [Hestroffer(2004)] Hestroffer, D. J. G. J. 2004. On Equilibrium Shapes among Binary Asteroids. *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society* 36, 07.10.

- [Hirabayashi et al.(2010)] Hirabayashi, M., Morimoto, M. Y., Kawaguchi, J. 2010. Two-Step Simulation for the Formation of Asteroid Itokawa from the Restricted Three-Body Problem to the Multi-Body Problem. *Transactions of Space Technology Japan* 7, .
- [Horner et al.(2003)] Horner, J., Evans, N. W., Bailey, M. E., Asher, D. J. 2003. The populations of comet-like bodies in the Solar system. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 343, 1057-1066.
- [Hughes and Chraibi(2011)] Hughes, G. B., Chraibi, M. 2011. Calculating ellipse overlap areas. *ArXiv e-prints arXiv:1106.3787*.
- [Ivezic et al.(2008)] Ivezic, Z., and 189 colleagues 2008. LSST: from Science Drivers to Reference Design and Anticipated Data Products. *ArXiv e-prints arXiv:0805.2366*.
- [Jacobson et al.(2014)] Jacobson, S., Scheeres, D., Rossi, A., Marzari, F., Davis, D. 2014. Both size-frequency distribution and sub-populations of the main-belt asteroid population are consistent with YORP-induced rotational fission. *Asteroids, Comets, Meteors 2014* .
- [Jeffreys(1923)] Jeffreys, H. 1923. Laplace's 'Exposition du Systeme du Monde'. *The Observatory* 46, 88-88.
- [Jewitt and Luu(1993)] Jewitt, D., Luu, J. 1993. Discovery of the candidate Kuiper belt object 1992 QB1. *Nature* 362, 730-732.
- [Jewitt et al.(1992)] Jewitt, D., Luu, J., Marsden, B. G. 1992. 1992 QB1. *International Astronomical Union Circular* 5611, 1.
- [Jewitt et al.(2014)] Jewitt, D., Agarwal, J., Li, J., Weaver, H., Mutchler, M., Larson, S. 2014. Disintegrating Asteroid P/2013 R3. *The Astrophysical Journal* 784, L8.
- [Johansen and Lacerda(2010)] Johansen, A., Lacerda, P. 2010. Prograde rotation of protoplanets by accretion of pebbles in a gaseous environment. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 404, 475-485.
- [Kant(1969)] Kant, I. 1969. *Universal natural history and theory of the heavens*. New introd. by Milton K. Munitz.. Ann Arbor] University of Michigan Press [1969] 1st ed. .
- [Kern and Elliot(2006)] Kern, S. D., Elliot, J. L. 2006. The Frequency of Binary Kuiper Belt Objects. *The Astrophysical Journal* 643, L57-L60.

- [Kuiper(1951)] Kuiper, G. P. 1951. On the Origin of the Solar System. Proceedings of the National Academy of Science 37, 1-14.
- [Lacerda(2011)] Lacerda, P. 2011. A Change in the Light Curve of Kuiper Belt Contact Binary (139775) 2001 QG₂₉₈. The Astronomical Journal 142, 90.
- [Lacerda(2008)] Lacerda, P. 2008. Detection of Contact Binaries Using Sparse High Phase Angle Light Curves. The Astrophysical Journal 672, L57.
- [Lacerda and Jewitt(2007)] Lacerda, P., Jewitt, D. C. 2007. Densities of Solar System Objects from Their Rotational Light Curves. The Astronomical Journal 133, 1393.
- [Leinhardt et al.(2010)] Leinhardt, Z. M., Marcus, R. A., Stewart, S. T. 2010. The Formation of the Collisional Family Around the Dwarf Planet Haumea. The Astrophysical Journal 714, 1789-1799.
- [Leonard(1930)] Leonard, F. C. 1930. The New Planet Pluto. Leaflet of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific 1, 121.
- [Leone et al.(1984)] Leone, G., Paolicchi, P., Farinella, P., Zappala, V. 1984. Equilibrium models of binary asteroids. Astronomy and Astrophysics 140, 265-272.
- [Levison et al.(2000)] Levison, H. F., Duncan, M. J., Zahnle, K., Holman, M., Dones, L. 2000. NOTE: Planetary Impact Rates from Ecliptic Comets. Icarus 143, 415-420.
- [Levison et al.(2008)] Levison, H. F., Morbidelli, A., Van Laerhoven, C., Gomes, R., Tsiganis, K. 2008. Origin of the structure of the Kuiper belt during a dynamical instability in the orbits of Uranus and Neptune. Icarus 196, 258-273.
- [Luu et al.(1993)] Luu, J., Jewitt, D., Marsden, B. G. 1993. 1993 FW. International Astronomical Union Circular 5730, 1.
- [Magnier(2006)] Magnier, E. 2006. The Pan-STARRS PS1 Image Processing Pipeline. The Advanced Maui Optical and Space Surveillance Technologies Conference E50.
- [Mann et al.(2007)] Mann, R. K., Jewitt, D., Lacerda, P. 2007. Fraction of Contact Binary Trojan Asteroids. The Astronomical Journal 134, 1133-1144.

- [Marcus et al.(2011)] Marcus, R. A., Ragozzine, D., Murray-Clay, R. A., Holman, M. J. 2011. Identifying Collisional Families in the Kuiper Belt. *The Astrophysical Journal* 733, 40.
- [Margot and Brown(2001)] Margot, J. L., Brown, M. E. 2001. Discovery and characterization of binary asteroids 22 Kalliope and 87 Sylvia. *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society* 33, 52.02.
- [Margot et al.(2002)] Margot, J. L., Nolan, M. C., Benner, L. A. M., Ostro, S. J., Jurgens, R. F., Giorgini, J. D., Slade, M. A., Campbell, D. B. 2002. Binary Asteroids in the Near-Earth Object Population. *Science* 296, 1445-1448.
- [Margot et al.(2002)] Margot, J. L., Trujillo, C., Brown, M. E., Bertoldi, F. 2002. The size and albedo of KBO 2002 AW197. *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society* 34, 17.03.
- [Margot(2002)] Margot, J.-L. 2002. Astronomy: Worlds of mutual motion. *Nature* 416, 694-695.
- [Marsden(1992)] Marsden, B. G. 1992. 1992 QB1. *International Astronomical Union Circular* 5633, 1.
- [Merline and Howell(1995)] Merline, W. J., Howell, S. B. 1995. A Realistic Model for Point-sources Imaged on Array Detectors: The Model and Initial Results. *Experimental Astronomy* 6, 163-210.
- [Morbidelli et al.(2005)] Morbidelli, A., Levison, H. F., Tsiganis, K., Gomes, R. 2005. Chaotic capture of Jupiter's Trojan asteroids in the early Solar System. *Nature* 435, 462-465.
- [Morbidelli and Levison(2004)] Morbidelli, A., Levison, H. F. 2004. Scenarios for the Origin of the Orbits of the Trans-Neptunian Objects 2000 CR₁₀₅ and 2003 VB₁₂ (Sedna). *The Astronomical Journal* 128, 2564-2576.
- [Movshovitz et al.(2015)] Movshovitz, N., Nimmo, F., Korycansky, D. G., Asphaug, E., Owen, J. M. 2015. Disruption and reaccretion of midsized moons during an outer solar system Late Heavy Bombardment. *Geophysical Research Letters* 42, 256-263.
- [Nesvorný et al.(2007)] Nesvorný, D., Vokrouhlický, D., Morbidelli, A. 2007. Capture of Irregular Satellites during Planetary Encounters. *The Astronomical Journal* 133, 1962-1976.

- [Noll et al.(2008)] Noll, K. S., Grundy, W. M., Stephens, D. C., Levison, H. F., Kern, S. D. 2008. Evidence for two populations of classical transneptunian objects: The strong inclination dependence of classical binaries. *Icarus* 194, 758-768.
- [Noll et al.(2002)] Noll, K. S., Stephens, D. C., Grundy, W. M., Millis, R. L., Spencer, J., Buie, M. W., Tegler, S. C., Romanishin, W., Cruikshank, D. P. 2002. Detection of Two Binary Trans-Neptunian Objects, 1997 CQ₂₉ and 2000 CF₁₀₅, with the Hubble Space Telescope. *The Astronomical Journal* 124, 3424-3429.
- [Opik(1951)] Opik, E. J. 1951. Collision probability with the planets and the distribution of planetary matter. *Proc. R. Irish Acad. Sect. A*, vol. 54, p. 165-199 (1951). 54, 165-199.
- [Osip et al.(2003)] Osip, D. J., Kern, S. D., Elliot, J. L. 2003. Physical Characterization of the Binary Edgeworth-Kuiper Belt Object 2001 QT₂₉₇. *Earth Moon and Planets* 92, 409-421.
- [Ostro et al.(2000)] Ostro, S. J., Hudson, R. S., Nolan, M. C., Margot, J.-L., Scheeres, D. J., Campbell, D. B., Magri, C., Giorgini, J. D., Yeomans, D. K. 2000. Radar Observations of Asteroid 216 Kleopatra. *Science* 288, 836-839.
- [Paddack and Rhee(1975)] Paddack, S. J., Rhee, J. W. 1975. Rotational bursting of interplanetary dust particles. *Geophysical Research Letters* 2, 365-367.
- [Paddack and Rubincam(2007)] Paddack, S. J., Rubincam, D. P. 2007. YORP: Origins and Outlook. *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society* 39, 5.01.
- [Rabinowitz et al.(2014)] Rabinowitz, D. L., Benecchi, S. D., Grundy, W. M., Ver-biscer, A. J. 2014. The rotational light curve of (79360) Sila-Nunam, an eclipsing binary in the Kuiper Belt. *Icarus* 236, 72-82.
- [Radzievskii(1952)] Radzievskii, V. V. 1952. A mechanism for the disintegration of asteroids and meteorites. *Astronomicheskii Zhurnal* 29, 162-170.
- [Ragozzine and Brown(2007)] Ragozzine, D., Brown, M. E. 2007. Candidate Members and Age Estimate of the Family of Kuiper Belt Object 2003 EL61. *The Astronomical Journal* 134, 2160-2167.
- [Richardson and Walsh(2006)] Richardson, D. C., Walsh, K. J. 2006. Binary Minor Planets. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences* 34, 47-81.

- [Rubincam(2000)] Rubincam, D. P. 2000. Radiative Spin-up and Spin-down of Small Asteroids. *Icarus* 148, 2-11.
- [Sánchez and Scheeres(2014)] Sánchez, P., Scheeres, D. J. 2014. The strength of regolith and rubble pile asteroids. *Meteoritics and Planetary Science* 49, 788-811.
- [Scheeres et al.(2000)] Scheeres, D. J., Ostro, S. J., Werner, R. A., Asphaug, E., Hudson, R. S. 2000. Effects of Gravitational Interactions on Asteroid Spin States. *Icarus* 147, 106-118.
- [Sheppard and Jewitt(2004)] Sheppard, S. S., Jewitt, D. 2004. Extreme Kuiper Belt Object 2001 QG₂₉₈ and the Fraction of Contact Binaries. *The Astronomical Journal* 127, 3023-3033.
- [Sierks et al.(2015)] Sierks, H., and 65 colleagues 2015. On the nucleus structure and activity of comet 67P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko. *Science* 347, aaa1044.
- [Slattery et al.(1991)] Slattery, W. L., Benz, W., Cameron, A. G. W. 1991. Effects of a giant impact on Uranus. *Lunar and Planetary Inst., 22nd Lunar and Planetary Science Conference* p 59-61 (SEE N91-19995 11-91) 22, .
- [Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory(2000)] Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory 2000. SAOImage DS9: A utility for displaying astronomical images in the X11 window environment. *Astrophysics Source Code Library ascl:0003.002*.
- [Steinberg and Sari(2011)] Steinberg, E., Sari, R. 2011. Binary YORP Effect and Evolution of Binary Asteroids. *The Astronomical Journal* 141, 55.
- [Stellingwerf(1978)] Stellingwerf, R. F. 1978. Period determination using phase dispersion minimization. *The Astrophysical Journal* 224, 953-960.
- [Stern(1991)] Stern, S. A. 1991. On the number of planets in the outer solar system - Evidence of a substantial population of 1000-km bodies. *Icarus* 90, 271-281.
- [Stern et al.(2015)] Stern, S. A., and 150 colleagues 2015. The Pluto system: Initial results from its exploration by New Horizons. *Science* 350, aad1815.
- [Szentgyorgyi et al.(2005)] Szentgyorgyi, A. H., Geary, J. G., Latham, D. W., Groner, L. T., Amato, S., Bennett, K., Falco, E. E., Peters, W. A., Ordway, M. P., Fata, R. G. 2005. KeplerCam. *Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society* 37, 110.10.

- [Tody(1986)] Tody, D. 1986. The IRAF Data Reduction and Analysis System. *Instrumentation in astronomy VI* 627, 733.
- [Trujillo(2008)] Trujillo, C. A. 2008. Future Surveys of the Kuiper Belt. *The Solar System Beyond Neptune* 573-585.
- [Vitense et al.(2010)] Vitense, C., Krivov, A. V., Löhne, T. 2010. The Edgeworth-Kuiper debris disk. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 520, A32.
- [Walsh and Richardson(2006)] Walsh, K. J., Richardson, D. C. 2006. Binary near-Earth asteroid formation: Rubble pile model of tidal disruptions. *Icarus* 180, 201-216.
- [Washabaugh and Scheeres(2002)] Washabaugh, P. D., Scheeres, D. J. 2002. Energy and Stress Distributions in Ellipsoids. *Icarus* 159, 314-321.
- [Weidenschilling(1989)] Weidenschilling, S. J. 1989. Stirring of a planetesimal swarm - The role of distant encounters. *Icarus* 80, 179-188.
- [Weidenschilling(1980)] Weidenschilling, S. J. 1980. Hektor - Nature and origin of a binary asteroid. *Icarus* 44, 807-809.
- [Weissman(1983)] Weissman, P. R. 1983. The mass of the Oort cloud. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 118, 90-94.
- [Weissman and Stern(1994)] Weissman, P. R., Stern, S. A. 1994. The impactor flux in the Pluto-Charon system. *Icarus* 111, 378-386.
- [Weisstein(2015)] Weisstein, Eric W. "Circle-Circle Intersection." From *MathWorld—A Wolfram Web Resource*. 2015. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/Circle-CircleIntersection.html>
- [Whipple(1964)] Whipple, F. L. 1964. Evidence for a Comet Belt beyond Neptune. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science* 51, 711-718.
- [Wijesinghe and Tedesco(1979)] Wijesinghe, M. P., Tedesco, E. F. 1979. A test of plausibility of eclipsing binary asteroids. *Icarus* 40, 383-393.
- [Wisdom(1982)] Wisdom, J. 1982. The origin of the Kirkwood gaps - A mapping for asteroidal motion near the 3/1 commensurability. *The Astronomical Journal* 87, 577-593.
- [Yu and Tremaine(1999)] Yu, Q., Tremaine, S. 1999. The Dynamics of Plutinos. *The Astronomical Journal* 118, 1873-1881.

[Zahnle et al.(2003)] Zahnle, K., Schenk, P., Levison, H., Dones, L. 2003. Cratering rates in the outer Solar System. *Icarus* 163, 263-289.